

**ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF THE NATIONAL POLICY ON HEALTH
WORKFORCE MIGRATION ON DOCTOR RETENTION RATES IN
PUBLIC HOSPITALS IN EDO STATE, NIGERIA**

BY

OSADOLOR, AISOSA JUNIOR

2024/B/MPA/0200

MIVA OPEN UNIVERSITY

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**A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF POSTGRADUATE STUDIES
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OPEN UNIVERSITY, ABUJA.**

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DECLARATION

I, Osadolor, Aisosa Junior [Mat No: 2024/B/MPA/0200], declare that this research titled Assessing the Impact of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration on Doctor Retention Rates in Public Hospitals in Edo State, Nigeria was carried out by me under the supervision of Chidozie, Felix, PhD. I attest that this dissertation has not been presented either wholly or partially for the award of any degree elsewhere. All sources of data and scholarly information used in this dissertation are duly acknowledged.

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CERTIFICATION

We certify that this dissertation titled *Assessing the Impact of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration on Doctor Retention Rates in Public Hospitals in Edo State, Nigeria* is an original research carried out by Osadolor, Aisosa Junior [Mat No: 2024/B/MPA/0200] in the Department of Public Policy and Administration, School of Management and Social Sciences, Abuja, Nigeria under the supervision of Chidozie, Felix PhD. We have examined and found this work acceptable as part of the requirements for the award of Master of Public Administration.

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Head of Department

Signature & Date

External Examiner

Signature & Date

Dean, School of Postgraduate Studies

Signature & Date

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to Edo State, my place of birth and origin, for being the comforting haven I proudly call home and the very framework upon which the core of my existence has taken shape. I also extend this dedication to all the conscientious Edo people who ardently strive to advance the state day by day.

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Osadolor, Aisosa Junior

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- HMA:** Hospitals Management Agency
- HRH:** Human Resources for Health
- LMICs:** Low- and Middle-Income Countries
- MDCAN:** Medical and Dental Consultants Association of Nigeria
- NMA:** Nigerian Medical Association
- M&E:** Monitoring and Evaluation
- MOUs:** Memoranda of Understanding
- NHWR:** National Health Workforce Registry
- NHRHP:** National Human Resources for Health Programme
- NPHWM:** National Policy on Health Workforce Migration
- SMART:** Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Time-bound
- UBTH:** University of Benin Teaching Hospital
- UK:** United Kingdom
- US:** United States
- WHO:** World Health Organisation

ABSTRACT

The persistent migration of medical doctors from Nigeria’s public health system poses a significant threat to healthcare delivery, equity, and the system’s sustainability. In response to this problem, the Federal Government of Nigeria introduced the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM) in 2024 as a coordinated framework to manage emigration while strengthening domestic retention. This study assessed the impact of the NPHWM on doctor retention in public hospitals in Edo State, focusing on policy awareness and perception, perceived effectiveness of policy interventions, and observed retention outcomes. Adopting a quasi-mixed-methods approach, primary data were collected from 112 medical and dental practitioners across the University of Benin Teaching Hospital and public secondary hospitals under the Edo State Hospitals Management Agency using a semi-structured questionnaire, complemented by retrospective institutional retention data for the period 2022–2025. Descriptive statistics, Spearman’s correlation, and binary logistic regression were used for analysis. Findings revealed a persistently high intention to migrate among respondents despite the policy’s introduction, driven mainly by low policy visibility and weak institutional domestication. While modest post-policy improvements in retention were observed in the tertiary hospital setting, secondary facilities continued to experience workforce instability. Work–life balance and safety showed the strongest bivariate association with retention intentions; however, policy awareness and perception, and international collaboration and ethical recruitment emerged as the only significant independent predictors of actual retention decisions. The study concludes that although the NPHWM is conceptually robust, its early implementation remains socially invisible and uneven across institutions. Strengthening communication, institutional uptake, and context-sensitive implementation is essential if the policy is to meaningfully mitigate doctor migration and stabilise Nigeria’s public health workforce.

Keywords: Doctor Retention, Edo State, Health Workforce Migration, Impact Assessment, National Policy on Health Workforce Migration

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The Nigerian healthcare system, like many others in sub-Saharan Africa, faces the challenge of human resource for health (HRH) incapacity (Falola & Ojebola, 2024; Orhungul et al., 2023). Among the most pressing of these challenges is the persistent migration of health professionals, including medical doctors and dentists, from the country's health system to more lucrative and stable opportunities abroad; a process termed human capital movement or flight. Human capital movement, also known as brain drain, is a prevalent global phenomenon, with countries such as Kenya, South Africa, Malaysia, Mexico, China, Iran, and even the United Kingdom (UK) experiencing significant losses of skilled talent in recent years (Ogbu, 2019). *Japa*, as it is commonly called in Nigeria, is characterised by the movement of highly skilled and educated individuals from a typically developing nation to another that is generally developed for a variety of reasons, including better remuneration, infrastructure, security, technology, and job satisfaction. (Ogbu, 2019). Brain drain has been posited to have adverse social, economic, and cultural implications for both nations involved, although these implications are more severe for the origin country (Carrington & Detragiache, 1999; Okwara, 2023). Brain drain among the health workforce in Nigeria can be traced back to the 1980s, even before the adoption of the Structural Adjustment Plan, which led to further economic woes and worsened its activity (Okwara, 2023). Many Nigerian healthcare workers migrated to Europe, North America, Asia, Australia, and the Middle East during the economic downturn that characterised this period (Okwara, 2023). Notable push factors encouraging brain drain include low remuneration, political instability and insecurity, demanding work environments with excessive workloads and stress, limited career advancement opportunities, irregular payment of salaries and allowances, inadequate funding and facilities (including training resources), preferential treatment among staff, and recruitment irregularities (Akafa et al., 2023; Akinola & Adekile, 2024; Akinyemi et al., 2022; Akinwale & George, 2022; Ebeye & Lee, 2023; Falola & Ojebola, 2024; Iloh et al., 2022; Oyedokun et al., 2025). Some of

the documented pull factors contributing to brain drain include better living and working conditions abroad, international demand for skilled healthcare workers, higher remuneration, and assurances of greater security (Iloh et al., 2022; Yarhere & Adeboye, 2023). These push and pull factors can be better understood through a proper examination of the theory of migration, also known as the intervening obstacle model, as proposed by Lee (1966).

Aside from the factors that trigger human capital flight, the emigration of skilled doctors has severe consequences for countries of origin, including adverse economic effects and unfavourable health outcomes, especially for maternal and child health in rural areas; it can also further weaken the healthcare system (Akinola & Adekile, 2024; Ebeye & Lee, 2023; Imafidon, 2018; Opara & Nsonwu, 2024).

The COVID-19 pandemic was a stark reminder of the damage caused by years of health workforce migration, highlighting the depth of dependence on a dwindling workforce. During this period, Nigeria was ranked as Africa's leading exporter of healthcare workers, further emphasising the urgency for policy intervention (Lawal et al., 2022). In response, the Federal Ministry of Health introduced the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM) in 2024. This policy aimed to strategically manage health worker migration by increasing domestic employee retention, aligning migration with ethical standards, establishing bilateral recruitment frameworks, and encouraging diaspora contributions (Federal Ministry of Health & Social Welfare, 2024). Employee retention refers to the process of attracting staff to remain with employer organisations for an extended period (Xuecheng et al., 2022). The NPHWM proposed incentive programmes and welfare enhancements, especially for those in rural and underserved areas. It also contained components such as capacity building, training, and research; digital health and technology integration; return, readmission, and reintegration programmes for those in the diaspora; work-life balance and well-being enhancement; health worker safety measures; and international collaborations/ethical recruitment (Federal Ministry of Health & Social Welfare, 2024). While comprehensive in scope, the NPHWM's actual impact on retention rates remains underexplored. Previous studies have focused on the retention rates of doctors and nurses without examining their relationship with the NPHWM (Alli, 2023; Falola & Ojebola, 2024; Orhungul et al., 2023).

Notwithstanding, many public healthcare facilities continue to report shortages, raising questions about the policy's implementation and efficacy. This study aims to address this gap by examining the impact of the NPHWM on the retention of doctors in public hospitals in Edo State. A mixed-methods research approach will be used to provide preliminary data on doctor retention and the association between policy retention strategies and retention rates.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Nigeria's healthcare delivery system is under severe strain, with one major contributing factor being the dwindling number of doctors in public hospitals (World Health Organisation [WHO], 2023). The migration of doctors has reached alarming proportions, prompting the Nigerian Medical Association (NMA) and other professional bodies to consistently raise concerns about the mass exodus. The NMA (2021) reported that less than half of the 80,000 registered Nigerian doctors were practising within the country, resulting in a doctor-population ratio of between 1:4,000 and 1:5,000, compared with the WHO-recommended ratio of 1:600 (Onah et al., 2022). In the same vein, the Medical and Dental Consultants Association of Nigeria (MDCAN), early in 2022, bemoaned that over 100 medical consultants had left 17 Nigerian tertiary health institutions in the preceding two years. A few months later, MDCAN surveyed its members and found that over 500 medical and dental consultants had left Nigeria for developed countries over the preceding few years, and nine out of every 10 consultants with less than five years of experience plan to leave the country for greener pastures (Onah et al., 2022). The shortage of qualified doctors has led to increased workloads and burnout among health workers, a decline in patient care quality, and, in extreme cases, the closure of specialised units due to a lack of staff (Adebayo et al., 2019; Akinwale & George, 2023; Ojuroungbe, 2023). Despite the launch of the NPHWM, there remains a lack of empirical data on its effectiveness in reversing these trends. Thus, this study critically assesses whether the policy has had any measurable impact on doctor retention in public hospitals in Edo State.

1.3 Research Questions

1. How do annual retention rates of doctors in selected public hospitals compare between the pre-NPHWM period (2022 – 2023) and the post-NPHWM period (2024 – 2025)?
2. What is the strength of the association between each core NPHWM intervention and doctors' decisions to remain in public service?
3. What actionable strategies and policy refinements can be recommended to enhance the effectiveness of the NPHWM in improving doctor retention?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

1.4.1 Main Objective

The main objective of this study is to assess the impact of the NPHWM on doctor retention rates in public hospitals in Edo State.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

To accomplish the primary objective, the following specific objectives will be pursued:

1. To quantify annual retention rates of doctors in selected public hospitals in Edo State, from 2022 to 2025, comparing pre- and post-NPHWM implementation.
2. To ascertain the association between key NPHWM interventions and doctors' retention decisions.
3. To proffer recommendations that will help refine the present policy.

1.5 Research Hypothesis

1.5.1 Null Hypothesis

H₀ 1: There is no statistically significant relationship between any NPHWM intervention and doctors' decisions to remain in public service.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study will be of great significance to multiple stakeholders. Policymakers and government agencies will benefit from empirical data that can inform future iterations of the NPHWM. Additionally, hospital administrators will gain valuable insights into effective human resource strategies from the study. Moreover, the study will provide healthcare professionals with an avenue to systematically document and integrate their experiences and perspectives into policy discourse. Academically, the study will contribute to the literature on migration, health governance, and policy evaluation in low-resource settings.

1.7 Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study examined the implementation of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM), with a specific focus on doctor retention in public hospitals in Edo State. The investigation will be confined to the 33 public secondary hospitals under the Edo State Hospitals Management Agency and the University of Benin Teaching Hospital. These facilities are distributed across both rural and urban areas of the state, allowing the study to capture variations in retention pressures, service conditions, and migration drivers across different geographic contexts. The study will not extend to private healthcare institutions or public primary healthcare facilities. These settings operate under distinct administrative and workforce dynamics and therefore fall outside the scope of this research's policy focus and analytical objectives.

Geographically, the restriction to Edo State was justified. The state operates a sizeable network of secondary hospitals serving both rural and urban populations, alongside a major tertiary referral centre. These facilities experience high patient volumes and are significantly affected by workforce migration, making Edo a suitable context for assessing the relevance and early outcomes of the NPHWM. The inclusion of rural hospitals was critical, as these settings often faced more acute retention challenges and provided critical insights into disparities in workforce stability.

The study period spanned six months, from July 2025 to December 2025. This timeframe was adequate for systematic data collection and analysis while remaining realistic within an academic research cycle. It also allowed integration of retrospective data (2022–2024) with

contemporaneous observations from the study period, thereby strengthening the evaluation of policy influence.

Temporally, the study focused on primary and secondary data covering 2022 to 2025. This range captures the pre-policy period and the immediate post-policy phase, enabling meaningful comparisons of retention patterns before and after the introduction of the NPHWM.

Finally, the study was limited to medical doctors and dental surgeons, excluding house officers, NYSC doctors, and other health professionals, such as nurses, pharmacists, and laboratory scientists. This delimitation aligned with the central aim of the NPHWM, which explicitly targets the stabilisation and retention of the medical and dental workforce. These groups have been among the most affected by recent migration trends.

1.8 Operational Definitions of Terms

Brain Drain: The loss of trained and talented professionals, particularly in specialised fields like medicine and dentistry, from a country due to emigration, typically resulting in a shortage of critical human capital in the source country.

Doctor Retention: For this study, retention will be defined as the continued employment of medical doctors or dental surgeons at the same public hospital in Benin City for at least 12 consecutive months, as verified by HR records.

Doctors: For this study, we will define doctors to include professionally certified medical doctors and dental surgeons.

Health Workforce Migration: The voluntary or involuntary movement of healthcare professionals from one country, region, or employment sector to another, often motivated by economic, political, or professional considerations.

Human Capital Movement/Flight: A broader term describing the emigration of educated and skilled individuals from one country to another, typically resulting in a net loss of expertise for the source country.

Japa: The colloquial name for brain drain in Nigeria.

National Policy on Health Workforce Migration: A Nigerian government policy framework introduced to manage the emigration of healthcare professionals through coordinated strategies such as workforce planning, ethical recruitment, bilateral agreements, and diaspora engagement.

Public Hospitals: Government-funded healthcare facilities that are responsible for providing accessible medical care to large populations.

Pull Factors: Attractive conditions in destination countries that draw healthcare professionals away from their home countries, such as better salaries, working conditions, advanced facilities, and structured career development.

Push Factors: Conditions within a source country that encourage the emigration of healthcare professionals, including poor remuneration, inadequate infrastructure, job insecurity, limited career advancement opportunities, and political instability.

Retention Rate: The percentage of doctors who remain employed in the same public hospital within 12 months after assumption of duty, without migrating to other countries or sectors.

Turnover Rate: The percentage of doctors who leave the employment of a public hospital within 12 months after assumption of duty, without migrating to other countries or sectors.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Preamble

Health workforce migration is one of the most pressing challenges undermining the resilience of health systems worldwide, and Nigeria has become one of the countries in sub-Saharan Africa most severely affected (World Health Organisation, 2024). The exodus of doctors and other skilled professionals from Nigeria's public health system has been described not only as a labour market crisis but also as a national security and development challenge (Falola & Ojebola, 2024). In recognition of this, the Federal Ministry of Health introduced the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration [NPHWM] in 2024, an initiative intended to balance the realities of emigration with domestic retention imperatives.

This chapter examines the conceptual and empirical literature, as well as the theoretical assumptions, relevant to doctor retention, workforce migration, and policy responses. The discussion begins with conceptual clarifications, then reviews empirical evidence from global, African, and Nigerian contexts, and finally highlights the knowledge gaps and the theoretical foundations underpinning this study.

2.2 Conceptual Review

To provide a clear framework for this study, it is essential to examine the key concepts that underpin health workforce dynamics and inform policy interventions. Conceptual reviews clarify the meanings, dimensions, and interrelationships of critical terms, ensuring that the study is grounded in both scholarly discourse and practical realities. In the context of doctor retention and health workforce migration, concepts such as retention, migration, and policy intervention are central to understanding the challenges and opportunities presented by the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM). Accordingly, the following concepts will be reviewed in this section:

- i. Doctor retention

- ii. Health workforce migration, and
- iii. Policy intervention in health systems.

2.3.1 Concept of Doctor Retention

Doctor retention refers to the sustained employment of medical practitioners within a health system over a defined period. It can be viewed as the converse of doctor turnover (Darbyshire et al., 2021; Falola & Ojebola, 2024). Retention rates are critical for ensuring continuity of care, reducing recruitment costs, and maintaining institutional capacity (De Vries et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2025). High retention rates reduce recruitment and training costs, preserve institutional knowledge, and enhance health system resilience, ultimately leading to improved quality of patient care (De Vries et al., 2023). Retention is especially critical in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), such as Nigeria, where shortages of healthcare workers are already acute. The World Health Organisation (WHO, 2023) has repeatedly emphasised that health workforce stability is a cornerstone of achieving Universal Health Coverage.

In the Nigerian context, retention challenges are heightened by multiple systemic weaknesses. Previous reports have shown that inadequate remuneration, irregular salary payments, and delayed promotions are significant determinants of exit intentions among doctors (Falola & Ojebola, 2024; Orhungul et al., 2023). Similarly, the quality of training, career growth opportunities, and the workplace environment influence whether doctors remain in service or migrate (Akinyemi et al., 2022; Falola & Ojebola, 2024). Thus, retention must be conceptualised as a multidimensional construct shaped by both extrinsic and intrinsic motivators.

2.2.2 Concept of Health Workforce Migration [Brain Drain / *Japa*]

Migration is a permanent or semi-permanent change in residence from one location to another (Agbaje et al., 2024). It can be internal or external, depending on the sovereign relationship between the destination and the origin location (Agbaje et al., 2024). Health workforce migration, often termed brain drain, is the movement of skilled healthcare workers from low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) to high-income countries (Ipinnimo et al., 2023). This movement has been reported to be driven by a combination of push factors [economic instability, poor

infrastructure, insecurity, limited professional growth] and pull factors [higher income, better working conditions, advanced technology, structured career pathways] (Umar et al., 2025).

In Nigeria, the migration phenomenon is commonly referred to as Japa. Reports show that, as of 2020, 3,895 Nigerian-trained medical doctors were practising in the United States [US] (Idowu, 2025). By July 2021, 4,528 of their counterparts were practising in the US (Idowu, 2025). Additionally, between 2017 and 2022, 57,000 nurses left Nigeria's shores to practise elsewhere (Idowu, 2025). The impact of such migration is severe, as it results in the loss of critical human capital, exacerbates inequities in healthcare provision, particularly in rural and underserved regions, and places additional burdens on the few doctors who remain (Tankwanchi et al., 2013). Migration has also been linked to broader socioeconomic consequences, such as a diminished potential for economic growth, despite the significant contribution of remittances from doctors in the diaspora (Korinya & Dansale, 2025). Moreover, unchecked migration erodes morale within the workforce that remains, creating cycles of attrition and undermining health service delivery (Ebeye & Lee, 2023).

2.2.3 Concept of Policy Intervention in Health Systems

Policy interventions in health systems are purposive actions designed to shape incentives, structures, and governance to achieve health system goals, such as accessibility, quality, efficiency, and sustainability (Maddox, 2024). In the context of health workforce migration, interventions often aim to reduce brain drain, improve retention, and balance individual rights to mobility with national health system needs (Omiyi et al., 2025).

From a theoretical standpoint, the health labour market and push–pull model [Lee's migration theory] explain why disparities in wages, working conditions, and career opportunities drive migration. Policy responses therefore aim to mitigate push factors, such as poor infrastructure and low remuneration, while counterbalancing pull factors, including higher pay and advanced training abroad (Oke, 2025). Ethical governance also plays a crucial role, as exemplified by the WHO Global Code of Practice, which promotes fair recruitment and international collaboration (Aistleithner & Pfabigan, 2016).

2.3.3.1 The National Policy on Health Workforce Migration

The National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM) constitutes Nigeria's comprehensive response to longstanding challenges of health workforce shortages, maldistribution, and international migration. Framed as both a retention and an engagement instrument, the policy articulates measures across incentives, capacity development, digital health, rural deployment, diaspora reintegration, safety, and governance. This section summarises the policy's principal provisions, critically appraises its design against implementation realities, and identifies implications for empirical research.

2.3.3.1.1 Policy Overview and Structure

The NPHWM is organised around interlocking thematic objectives:

- (i) incentivising service in rural and underserved areas
- (ii) strengthening capacity and institutions for training and professional development
- (iii) mainstreaming digital health and cross-border interoperability
- (iv) improving rural deployment through amenities and career pathways
- (v) facilitating return, readmission, and reintegration of diaspora health professionals
- (vi) protecting worker wellbeing and safety
- (vii) promoting ethical recruitment and international cooperation.

For each theme, the policy outlines institutional responsibilities, financing expectations, and monitoring arrangements, most notably through the National Health Workforce Registry (NHWR) and the proposed National Human Resources for Health Programme (NHRHP).

2.3.3.1.2 Thematic Summary

- i. **Incentives and welfare:** The policy mandates targeted incentive packages to retain health workers in rural and underserved locations, including access to special credit facilities, tax incentives for investors, mortgage schemes, expanded insurance coverage, and periodic salary and allowance reviews. It also commits to ensuring that adequate equipment and

supplies are available to improve working conditions. These measures explicitly combine financial support with material improvements to the workplace environment.

- ii. **Capacity building and institutional development:** The NPHWM emphasises continuous professional development, formal career pathways, and institutional upgrades through technology transfer. It calls for partnerships with destination countries to create skills partnerships and mechanisms to both increase local training capacity and formalise mutually beneficial exchanges.
- iii. **Digital health and technology integration:** The policy outlines an expansive digital health agenda, encompassing telemedicine, electronic health records, interoperability standards, cross-border data governance, and capacity-building for remote and tele-practice. It requires funding for broadband and digital infrastructure and directs regulators to update codes of practice for safe digital health delivery. The NPHWM also links digital health implementation to diaspora co-practice and cross-jurisdictional supervision.
- iv. **Rural and underserved area support:** The document operationalises rural deployment through:
 - a. career pathways that credit rural service
 - b. a *one facility per ward* construction objective
 - c. incentives for private sector investment in rural centres
 - d. commitments to provide essential social amenities and decent accommodation.

It further mobilises intergovernmental structures, the National Council on Health/National Economic Council and the NHWR, to coordinate deployment.

- v. **Return, readmission, and reintegration:** The policy outlines practical steps for diaspora engagement and returnee reintegration: coordinated return via designated agencies, soft loans and grants for returnees establishing facilities, mandatory continuous professional development refresher and re-certification courses, and institutional support from the Nigerians in Diaspora Commission and other agencies for housing, financial advice, and career placement.

- vi. **Work-life balance, wellbeing, and safety:** The NPHWM mandates the inclusion of work-life balance content in training curricula, measures to ensure adequate staffing to reduce burnout, and the establishment of formalised mental health protections. It explicitly requires the provision of Personal Protective Equipment, routine health checks, insurance, standardised safety guidelines, emergency response protocols, and measures to criminalise violence against health workers.
- vii. **International collaboration and ethical recruitment:** The policy prioritises Memoranda of Understanding (MOUs) and bilateral and multilateral agreements, which are designed to be mutually beneficial and aligned with global norms on ethical recruitment. It also proposes a migration system for tracked, ethical recruitment and calls on destination countries to invest in Nigerian training infrastructure as part of skills partnerships.
- viii. **Monitoring, data, and governance:** Central to the NPHWM is the NHWR and the NHRHP institutional architecture. The policy requires routine data collection, reporting by regulatory bodies and embassies, monitoring and evaluation (M&E) systems, and periodic policy reviews (every five years) to enable evidence-based adjustments.

2.3.3.1.3 Critical Appraisal

- i. **Strengths:** The NPHWM is commendable for its comprehensiveness: it addresses both push (working conditions, career progression) and pull (ethical recruitment, bilateral engagement) factors and institutionalises data systems (NHWR) to enable targeted action. The explicit linkage of digital health to diaspora co-practice and cross-border interoperability is forward-looking and, if implemented, could materially reduce service gaps.
- ii. **Risks and constraints:** The policy's ambitions are resource-intensive. Core commitments, salary reviews, mortgages, one facility per ward, and nationwide digital infrastructure require predictable budgetary allocations and sustained interministerial coordination. However, fiscal constraints and fragmented implementation capacity at the state and local levels create significant delivery risks. The digital agenda confronts persistent rural connectivity and power deficits that will reduce the immediate reach of telehealth unless

mitigations are prioritised. Finally, the success of diaspora and bilateral arrangements will depend on diplomatic bargaining, enforceable MOUs, and reliable tracking via the NHWR.

- iii. **Governance and accountability:** The NPHWM assigns responsibilities across ministries and agencies and prescribes M&E. However, empirical experience with similarly complex health reforms in Nigeria shows that without clear accountability lines, independent auditing, and civil society engagement, implementation can be uneven. Strengthening transparency (public dashboards from the NHWR and independent evaluations) would reduce the risk of implementation gaps and help capture problems early.

2.3.3.1.4 Conclusion

The NPHWM is a strategically coherent and evidence-informed policy instrument that addresses the multifaceted drivers of health workforce migration. Its long-term success will depend on realistic, sequenced implementation, beginning with robust data systems (NHWR), pilot testing of incentive bundles, and targeted investments in rural infrastructure and digital connectivity. For researchers, the policy offers fertile ground for generating operational evidence to refine and prioritise interventions that are both effective and fiscally sustainable.

2.3.3.2 Incentives and Welfare

One of the most widely used policy interventions is the use of financial incentives. Credit facilities, housing/mortgage schemes, insurance coverage, and reviewed salaries/allowances could be utilised to encourage health workers to remain in employment, especially those in rural services. Previous reports corroborate this assertion, acknowledging the significant influence of salary enhancements and hardship allowances on employee retention decisions (Adzei & Atinga, 2012; Arnold et al., 2022; Fenyi & Keelson, 2025).

Improvements in infrastructure, governance, and workplace culture are equally crucial; research shows that poor working conditions are a substantial *push* factor for migration (Okunade & Awosusi, 2023; Olumoyo & Abiri, 2023). Other studies have shown a significant relationship between the physical, mental, psychological, and social work environment and worker retention (Hamal et al., 2023; Hoang, 2024). These findings suggest that a positive, encouraging work environment leads to higher worker retention. Moreover, Dumitriu et al. (2025) corroborated this

assertion, reporting that an appropriate work environment contributed to worker well-being and, hence, work-life balance, which could, in turn, positively impact retention rates (Dumitriu et al., 2025).

2.3.3.3 Capacity Building, Training, and Research

Opportunities for structured professional growth, such as specialist training, residency expansion, and continuing education, also serve as retention tools. Keitu (2024) emphasises that career development interventions not only address migration but also improve job satisfaction and performance. One would expect that doctors who perceive a clear progression path would be less inclined to seek opportunities abroad, even though migration intentions are usually multifactorial. A previous report by Oladeji et al. (2022) showed that non-financial incentives, such as career advancement opportunities and continued professional development, were significant job-retention motivators among the studied sample.

In addition, the creation of exchange programmes and research networks between institutions in origin and destination locations, which is a means of technology transfer, has been highlighted as having great potential for combating brain drain (Radwan & Sakr, 2020)

2.3.3.4 Digital Health Adoption and Technology Integration

Digital health refers to the use of information and communication technologies to deliver healthcare (Adekoya et al., 2023). Its advantages include improved access to health records, provision of remote services, delivery of health information via mobile devices, and enhanced knowledge for healthcare workers (Adekoya et al., 2023). The use of digital health technology has been cited as leveraging the globalisation advantages of internet technology, whereby, for example, patients in Nigeria could consult and obtain treatment from a Nigerian doctor in Ghana or the UK (AUDA-NEPAD, 2021). In addition, integrating digital health technology into the Nigerian health system offers opportunities for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and technology transfer with brain drain destination nations (AUDA-NEPAD, 2021). Notwithstanding the potential for digital health technology adoption to create issues with individual differences in the rate of adoption of technology and change is substantial. Digital technology can increase workloads and complexity for those with digital illiteracy, and the need for digital security literacy measures adds another layer of stress and demotivation for those concerned (Egwuno et al., 2025).

2.3.3.5 Return, Readmission, and Reintegration of Health Workers

According to Lee's (1966) migration theory, every migration stream has a substantial counter stream of return migration [Figure 1]. Return migration has been portrayed as a complex experience for returnees, in part because of the challenges of readjusting to life and adapting to the current environment (Efendi et al., 2021).

Moreover, stigmatisation, underutilisation or non-utilisation of one's professional skills, challenges in re-entering the labour market, and the need to adapt to context-specific inefficiencies remain discouraging (Efendi et al., 2021; Oklikah et al., 2024). Return migration benefits countries of origin by transferring both financial and human capital accumulated in countries of destination (Wahba, 2015). This benefit, however, depends on the returnee acquiring skills, knowledge, and financial resources while in the destination country, as well as on a functional return, readmission, and reintegration policy that can assist in investing these skills and resources in the origin country (Wahba, 2015).

2.2.3.6 Work-Life Balance and Wellbeing

Work-life balance is the equilibrium between one's job and personal life activities (Vidani et al., 2024). It is reported to affect productivity and contribute to stress and burnout, prompting consideration of a job and/or residence change (Anees et al., 2021; Vidani et al., 2024). A previous report in Greece highlighted how flexible working-hour arrangements, among other factors, played a pivotal role in mitigating brain drain (Efthalitsidou et al., 2025). Similarly, findings from Alhebshi et al. (2024) indicate that enhancing worker well-being is associated with increased job satisfaction, which, in turn, positively affects turnover intentions. Furthermore, Ogunsuji et al. (2019) conducted a systematic review of four studies to estimate the prevalence and correlates of burnout among Nigerian physicians and to draw implications for workforce retention. The review reported burnout prevalences ranging from 23.6% to 51.7%, with resident/early-career doctors showing the highest burden. Major predictors included young age, excessive workload, poor working conditions, and psychosocial stressors. The authors recommended routine monitoring of physician well-being, reductions in workload, improved supervision and mentoring for trainees, and further high-quality national studies to characterise the problem better. They concluded that physician burnout, an upstream driver of emigration risk, remains substantial in Nigeria and requires institutional and system-level responses to improve retention.

2.2.3.7 Health Worker Safety

Safety in the workplace entails creating and maintaining a work environment and work procedures free from hazards that could cause injury or even death (Adetunji et al., 2022). While the workplace infrastructure needs to be optimal to avoid hazardous threats, it is also important for the built environment to be secure; this expectation has become imperative given the rising incidence of banditry and kidnapping in Nigeria. For example, Okojie and Ahmad (2022) recount how many primary health care facilities in Zamfara State have been deserted by staff because of bandit attacks, with instances of armed bandits kidnapping and sexually assaulting healthcare workers being common. A similar situation is responsible for the destruction of two primary healthcare facilities and the temporary shutdown of another sixty-nine in Katsina State (Sani et al., 2024). Such ordeals alone are enough to breed dissatisfaction in a previously satisfied health worker.

Alongside the built environment being safe, the safety of the workplace also encompasses protecting health workers from events such as violence, abuse, harassment, and assault while on duty. With the increasing turnover of health workers in Nigeria, driven by myriad factors that lead to job dissatisfaction, the inability to guarantee the safety and security of health workers on the job could significantly contribute to turnover intentions (Adebite & Babatunde, 2024). Given that prevalence values in previous studies ranged from 16.7% to 88.1%, it is alarming that these occurrences have been largely overlooked until recently (Elom et al., 2024; Ilikannu et al., 2025; Isara, 2023; Isara et al., 2024).

Given the foregoing disturbing statistics on insecurity and violence against health workers in Nigeria, it is not surprising that even if a health worker were to factor in no other variable, he or she would still want to emigrate (Ogwo, 2023).

2.3.3.8 International Collaborations and Ethical Recruitment

At the global level, international frameworks seek to regulate and balance migration flows. The WHO Global Code of Practice promotes ethical recruitment and fair treatment of health personnel from countries with critical shortages of HRH (Aistleithner & Pfabigan, 2016). This initiative involves government-to-government agreements with conditions to ensure assistance in achieving the development goals of the health workforce system at its origin (Clemens &

Dempster, 2021). Furthermore, the introduction of global skill partnerships between nations of origin and destination has also been proposed (Clemens & Dempster, 2021). This initiative is a bilateral or multilateral agreement between equal partners, in which the country/countries of destination agree to provide technology and finance to train potential migrants with targeted skills in the country of origin before they migrate, and ultimately welcome these migrants with precisely the skills they need to integrate best and contribute upon arrival. The country of origin agrees to provide training and receives support for training non-migrants as well, thereby increasing rather than draining human capital (Clemens & Dempster, 2021).

Global evidence from 1960 to 2020 suggests that signing a bilateral labour agreement increases migration from an origin country to a destination country by 76 per cent in the decade following the signing (Adhikari et al., 2024). However, concerns remain that these agreements serve as a tool for regularising the already existing migration trend (Clemens, 2024). The literature map of the concepts reviewed so far is depicted below [Figure 3].

Figure 1

A Literature Map of the Concepts Reviewed in the Present Study.

Source: Principal investigator (2025)

2.2.4 Conceptual Model

The conceptual model, grounded in the conceptual review, illustrates how independent variables, principally the intervention components of the NPHWM, affect doctor retention through a set of intervening [mediating] and moderating variables. These variables can either promote or inhibit retention outcomes, depending on the efficiency and credibility of policy implementation. Intervening variables, such as awareness, perceived credibility, timeliness of incentives, and job satisfaction, explain the mechanisms through which policy signals translate into behavioural outcomes. Moderating variables, including hospital type, cadre, and broader political-economic conditions, not only shape the strength and direction of these relationships but may also directly

influence retention. Together, the model emphasises that doctor retention is not determined solely by policy inputs, but by their interaction with organisational processes and contextual factors.

Figure 2

The Present Study's Conceptual Model

Source: Principal investigator (2025)

The figure above shows the relationships among independent, moderating, and mediating variables and how they interact to influence the dependent (outcome) variable.

2.3 Empirical Review

This section presents an empirical review of studies relevant to the focus of this research. It examines previous empirical findings to establish what has been investigated, the methodologies employed, and the important results reported by different scholars. By synthesising evidence from related studies, this review highlights patterns, consistencies, and contradictions in the literature and identifies gaps that justify the need for the present study.

2.3.1 Global Experiences

Poudel et al. (2018) conducted a mixed-methods study to explore the migration intentions of nursing students in Nepal. The researchers surveyed 799 nursing students and conducted 12 semi-structured interviews to obtain deeper qualitative insights. Their findings indicated that 92.5% of respondents intended to migrate, with three-quarters motivated by the opportunity to pursue further education abroad. Regression analysis showed that students with lower professional identity and those who had not chosen nursing as their first career option were significantly more likely to express migration intentions. Interview findings highlighted systemic push factors, including low salaries, unemployment, poor working conditions, and limited opportunities for postgraduate education and professional autonomy in Nepal. The authors recommended expanding postgraduate training opportunities, improving working conditions, and enhancing the professional image of nursing to reduce migration intentions among future health workers.

Zapata et al. (2025) conducted a policy analysis to assess the effectiveness of Romania's interventions in reducing physician emigration to WHO European countries. The researchers analysed migration trends using administrative and international migration data, complemented by a review of national policy documents and health workforce statistics. Their findings show that the annual migration of Romanian doctors decreased from 1,532 in 2012 to 461 in 2021, representing a reduction of approximately two-thirds. This decline was associated with policy measures, including financial incentives (notably, salary increases beginning around 2017-2018), infrastructure improvements in health facilities, expansion of residency and medical education opportunities, and enhancements to research and working conditions. They recommend that sustained retention effects require continued investment not only in remuneration but also in improving working environments, expanding speciality training and residency slots (especially in family medicine), and strengthening non-salary motivators, alongside clear regulatory and educational reforms.

In a similar study by Ognyanova et al. (2014), which utilised a qualitative research methodology with a three-stage method (survey, interview, and focus group discussion), notable themes among emigrated respondents or those with emigration intentions included increased workloads, a need for greater responsibility, work culture, a desire for personal recognition, and

poor working conditions. The destination countries among these respondents included Switzerland, Tanzania, and New Zealand.

Murphy et al. (2016) conducted a mixed-methods study to examine the drivers, consequences, and management of health worker migration in Jamaica. The researchers used surveys of physicians, nurses, midwives, and dental auxiliaries, as well as structured interviews with representatives from government ministries, professional associations, regional health authorities, healthcare facilities, and training institutions. Their findings revealed that migration remains widespread, driven mainly by systemic disparities in living and working conditions between Jamaica and destination countries. The study also highlighted the lack of robust systems for monitoring migration, which limits the ability to assess its impact fully. Although several national and international initiatives aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of migration were identified, there was limited evidence of practical implementation. The authors recommended strengthening information systems to track migration formally, updating the national cadre system for health personnel, enforcing bonding policies equitably, and providing both formal and informal recognition for health workers.

Toyin-Thomas et al. (2023) conducted a systematic review of the drivers of health-worker migration, migration intention, and non-migration in LMICs. The authors searched five major databases for studies published between 1970 and 2022 and screened over 21,000 records. The review included 107 studies (82 single-country studies and 25 multi-country studies), analysed cadre coverage and trends, and coded drivers at the macro, meso, and micro levels. They found that remuneration (83.2%) and security problems (58.9%) were the dominant macro-level push factors, while career prospects (81.3%), a good working environment (63.6%), and job satisfaction (57.9%) were the main meso-level drivers. These patterns were stable over decades and consistent across cadres. The authors recommended comprehensive national workforce planning, pay and security reforms, expanded local specialist training, and regulation of international recruitment, arguing that multi-level interventions tailored to national fiscal realities are needed. They concluded that LMICs should adapt tested multi-level strategies while tailoring details to local constraints.

Finally, Ung et al. (2024) conducted a mixed-methods systematic review to examine the factors influencing the retention of Asian internationally educated nurses in destination countries.

The review analysed 27 studies published between 2013 and 2022 across Asia, Australia, Europe, North America, the Middle East, and Africa. The findings indicated that although many nurses migrated in search of better career prospects, they often encountered occupational downgrading due to difficulties with credential recognition. Additional barriers to retention included disparities in career advancement opportunities, mismatches in the scope of practice between the origin and destination countries, challenges with cultural and linguistic adaptation, and the absence of adequate social or family support systems. The authors recommended a range of strategies to improve retention, including granting permanent residency or stable immigration status, ensuring transparent credentialing and registration processes, promoting equity in professional development and career progression, instituting tailored orientation and induction programmes, and facilitating family reunification support for migrating nurses.

2.3.2 African Context

Oke (2025) conducted a systematic review of 51 data sources (36 peer-reviewed studies and 15 grey literature items) to identify practical solutions to mitigate health-care workforce migration in Africa. The researchers reviewed literature published between 2014 and 2024, drawing on databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and WHO repositories, as well as policy reports and other non-academic sources. The author's findings indicate that the most frequently cited solutions include enhancing professional training and career development opportunities, providing financial incentives, improving working conditions, and initiating and reinforcing international collaborations. Proposed implementation strategies included addressing wage disparities, offering mentorship programmes, creating competitive postgraduate training programmes, and enhancing the workplace environment. The author concludes that sustainable mitigation of health workforce migration in Africa will require multi-sectoral coordination and structural reforms that go beyond salary increases alone.

Adam et al. (2025) conducted a scoping review to examine African nurses' migration decisions, destination preferences, and recruitment practices. The review included 28 studies (21 peer-reviewed, seven grey literature) published since 2000. Their findings indicated that African nurses' migration is driven chiefly by economic hardship and income disparities at home, as well as by career development and a lack of stable employment. Colonial ties, shared language or

culture, and ease of integration influence these nurses' destination choices. Recruitment practices often involve international inter-agency collaborations and direct recruitment by health systems in destination countries. They recommended stronger regulation of recruitment, improvements in home-country working conditions (including career pathways and job stability), and policies that account for cultural and linguistic compatibility to reduce barriers in destination countries.

Labonté et al. (2015) conducted a four-country cross-sectional study to examine the drivers and consequences of skilled health worker migration, as well as strategies to mitigate its adverse effects. The researchers surveyed physicians, nurses, pharmacists, and dentists, and interviewed key stakeholders across Jamaica, India, the Philippines, and South Africa. Their findings in South Africa indicated a decline in skilled health worker out-migration since the early 2000s, attributed mainly to reduced demand for foreign-trained professionals, stricter recruitment practices, and tighter migration policies in destination countries. Despite persistently low job satisfaction, the 2007 Occupation Specific Dispensation (OSD) policy, which significantly increased wages, was found to play a crucial role in retaining nurses. Return migration was reported as common, and while the consequences of migration remained mixed, the severity of workforce shortages had lessened. The authors concluded that the most effective retention initiatives are those that strengthen the South African health system internally.

Vidal (2015) conducted a qualitative analysis of the emigration of health-care workers from Malawi and its impact on the national health system, utilising secondary data from government and international sources. His findings were as follows: by the early 2000s, 59% of Malawian-trained doctors and 16% of nurses were working abroad, resulting in critical shortages and nursing vacancy rates approaching 80%. In response, the Emergency Human Resources Program (EHRP, 2004–2009) implemented a 52% salary increase, expanded training, and recruited international volunteers. These measures reduced nurse emigration from 108 in 2003 to 16 in 2009 and increased health worker density by 66%. Despite these improvements, challenges such as wage gaps with developed countries, inadequate infrastructure, corruption, and reliance on expatriate staff persisted. Vidal concluded that while the EHRP provided temporary relief, Malawi's health system continues to face significant workforce challenges that require comprehensive reforms in retention, management, and governance.

Finally, Obianagwa et al. (2025) conducted a qualitative study to assess the effectiveness of the NPHWM's incentive system in reducing the migration of trained healthcare workers. The

researchers analysed secondary data from academic publications, government reports, and media sources. Their findings indicate that current Federal Government initiatives through the NPHWM have not produced significant improvements. They recommended establishing a Health Sector Bank in Nigeria to facilitate the timely and consistent payment of increased salaries and allowances. They also advocated providing low-interest loans and grants to healthcare professionals to support the establishment of practices and research activities within Nigeria.

2.3.3 Nigerian Studies

Samuel and Jonah (2025) conducted a narrative review to analyse the brain drain of Nigerian nurses to the United Kingdom, synthesising evidence and reports (peer-reviewed articles, regulatory data, and primary news sources) published primarily between 2022 and 2024. The authors conducted extensive database and web searches (PubMed, Google Scholar, AJOL, WHO, nursing council reports, and national press) and synthesised counts and trends where available. The review identified occupational dissatisfaction, sociopolitical instability, delayed or irregular pay, and inadequate social welfare support as the leading push factors; it also noted the presence of active and streamlined recruitment pathways in destination countries. Recommended actions included expanding local retention strategies (such as technology-enabled workforce planning and phased retirement options), improving social welfare and pay regularity, and undertaking evaluation research to measure the impact of these interventions. The authors concluded that urgent, evaluated policy action is required to stabilise Nigeria's nursing workforce.

Olorunfemi et al. (2024) conducted a narrative review of "Japa Syndrome" among Nigerian nurses and practical retention strategies. The authors conducted a systematic search of peer-reviewed literature, policy reports, and media sources from 2018 to 2024, synthesising evidence on drivers, impacts, and interventions. Their review found that the recent surge in nurse emigration is driven primarily by chronic low pay, unsafe or resource-poor workplaces, frequent pay disruptions, limited continuing-education opportunities, and a perceived lack of recognition; consequences include critical staffing gaps, higher workloads, and worsening patient outcomes. Recommended interventions emphasised (1) enforceable and timely pay mechanisms, (2) occupational safety and supply-chain improvements, (3) structured career and postgraduate training paths, (4) non-salary incentives (housing, low-interest start-up loans, protected study

leave), and (5) active diaspora engagement (knowledge transfer, short-term placements). The authors concluded that multi-pronged, enforceable policy packages targeting both push factors and institutional governance are required to curb the Japa wave.

Onah et al. (2022) conducted a national cross-sectional survey of physicians to assess emigration intentions and their correlates in Nigeria. The authors administered a structured questionnaire to a broad sample of physicians (N = 913) across states and analysed responses using descriptive statistics and multivariable logistic regression. The study found that only 13.0% of physicians were satisfied with their work, and 19.3% were willing to continue practising in Nigeria. In comparison, 43.9% had decided to emigrate, and 36.8% were undecided about their plans. The most frequently reported push factors were poor remuneration (91.3%), rising insecurity (79.8%), and inadequate diagnostic/clinical facilities (61.8%). Older physicians and those satisfied with their work were more likely to remain in practice, while those in public facilities reported lower job satisfaction. The authors recommended urgent policy reforms, including improved and regular remuneration, investments in clinical infrastructure, enhanced workplace security, and strengthened human-resource management (mentorship, career progression). They concluded that without systemic reforms to pay, safety, and facility capacity, physician emigration will continue to threaten the resilience of Nigeria's health system.

Wariri et al. (2024) conducted a 15-year retrospective cohort study of doctors and dentists who graduated from a Nigerian medical school to characterise migration patterns and their determinants. Using institutional graduation records linked to professional registration and reported destination outcomes, the authors tracked cohort members over 15 years and modelled migration probabilities by graduation year and cohort. The study found a large outflow: nearly half of the graduates had emigrated within 15 years, with migration rates accelerating after about 2016, a pattern associated with worsening insecurity and relative declines in local remuneration and training opportunities, as analysed. The authors recommended strengthening postgraduate training capacity, improving early-career working conditions, and implementing alumni/diaspora engagement and bonding options tied to funded specialist training to reduce long-term graduate attrition. They concluded that cohort tracking shows the problem is structural and accelerating, so interventions must combine training expansion with retention financing.

Yakubu et al. (2023) conducted a concurrent mixed-methods study (a cross-sectional survey and semi-structured interviews) to map the scope of skilled health-worker migration governance in Nigeria and to link governance dimensions to migration intentions. The authors developed and administered a 46-item survey to nurses, pharmacists, dentists, and doctors, and performed exploratory factor analysis and multivariate modelling. They also conducted 22 qualitative interviews and performed thematic analysis. Analyses identified eight governance factors (e.g., government efforts to promote economic and political stability, collaborative approaches, workforce policies, rights-based governance). They revealed that weak governance, poor accountability to rules and norms, and limited stakeholder engagement were associated with higher migration intentions. Interviews highlighted poor implementation of existing policies, payroll failures, and governance gaps at the constitutional level. The authors recommended a rights-based, whole-of-government governance approach, which involves strengthening accountability, engaging professional associations and civil society, expanding funded training, and adopting collaborative, regionally informed policies that align with human rights norms. They concluded that improving migration governance (not just isolated pay fixes) is essential to reduce emigration intentions among Nigeria's skilled health workers.

2.3.4 Edo State

Olorunfemi et al. (2020) conducted a descriptive cross-sectional survey to assess the impact of nurse emigration on health-care delivery in Benin City, Edo State. The researchers used a stratified sampling approach to recruit 270 nurses from three hospitals (University of Benin Teaching Hospital, n=155; Edo State Central Hospital, n=80; Faith Mediplex, n=35) and administered a self-structured questionnaire with Likert scales and open-ended questions. Data were analysed, and descriptive and inferential statistics were computed. The study found clear evidence that nurse emigration worsens staffing shortages and workloads (mean impact score reported: 1.59 ± 0.92), reduces the quality of care, and contributes to higher morbidity and mortality indicators in the sampled facilities. There was no significant difference in reasons for emigration by gender. The authors recommended that short-term palliatives (increased training intake) be complemented by structural measures, including stable and competitive pay, consistent payroll, improved working conditions, and investments in clinical infrastructure, to prevent further attrition. They concluded that Benin City hospitals face service-delivery risks from continued nurse outflows unless systemic reforms are implemented.

Okolo & Iruo (2021) conducted a cross-sectional predictive study to examine the perceived determinants of brain drain among mental health care professionals in specialist health facilities in Benin City, Edo State. The authors administered the “Brain Drain Prediction Scale” to 299 respondents [277 from the Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital and 72 from the University of Benin Teaching Hospital] using purposive sampling. The data were analysed and reported as frequencies and percentages; a chi-square test was also computed to assess the association. The study found that mental health care professionals perceive strong associations between poor working conditions, a lack of professional development opportunities, low remuneration, and brain drain intention. A statistically significant relationship was found between several of these perceived push factors and the predicted intention to emigrate. They recommended improving remuneration, creating clear professional career paths, enhancing the workplace environment, and providing better equipment and mental health support. They concluded that mental health professionals in Benin City see brain drain not as vague or distant, but as materially tied to modifiable workplace and policy conditions.

Esene et al. (2024) conducted a descriptive cross-sectional study to assess the prevalence, pattern, and determinants of brain drain among healthcare workers in suburban Edo State. The study used a sample of 320 health workers selected via cluster sampling; data were collected using a pre-tested self-administered questionnaire and analysed using SPSS for descriptive statistics and tests of association (Chi-square). The findings showed a high prevalence of brain drain intention among health workers; limited educational opportunities were the most frequently cited push factor (98.3%), and recognition of professional expertise was the top pull factor (98.3%). There was a strong statistical relationship between the socioeconomic and political conditions of the home country and the prevalence of brain drain. They recommended that the government take responsibility for improving educational opportunities, recognising professionals, enhancing remuneration, and providing professional incentives. They concluded that brain drain among health professionals in Edo State is widespread and strongly associated with both educational and recognition/pull factors; thus, urgent intervention is needed.

In a similar enquiry, Shaidrova (2022) conducted an ethnographic study of returnee migrants in Benin City, Edo State, to examine how returnees perform social identity, negotiate stigma, and reintegrate into local life. The researcher conducted extended ethnographic fieldwork

(participant observation, in-depth interviews, and informal conversations) with returnees, families, and local actors in Benin City over multiple visits; data were analysed using thematic and narrative methods. Findings showed that returnees actively perform a “returnee” identity that mixes pride and shame: while remittances and new skills can boost household status, many returnees face stigma, trauma (particularly those who passed through irregular routes), and limited economic opportunities on return. Reintegration was found to be gendered; women often experienced more precarious labour-market outcomes and heightened social scrutiny, and social networks mediated access to resources and re-employment. The author recommended coordinated reintegration support (psychosocial services, skills certification and recognition, livelihood programmes), safer/legal migration pathways (information campaigns and regulation of smugglers), and targeted support for female returnees. Shaidrova concluded that policymakers in Edo State should treat returnee flows not only as security or criminal issues, but also as opportunities for productive reintegration that require social services, skills recognition, and community-based interventions.

2.4 Gaps in Literature

Despite the expanding literature on health workforce migration and doctor retention, notable gaps persist in understanding how national policy responses translate into measurable retention outcomes, particularly within sub-national public health systems. These gaps include those related to policy impact, local context, implementation, and policy adoption and adaptation.

2.4.1 Policy Impact

The Federal Government’s National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (Federal Ministry of Health & Social Welfare, 2024) outlines incentives, diaspora engagement, monitoring (by the NHWR), and aims for bilateral/ethical recruitment; however, a targeted, peer-reviewed impact evaluation measuring the policy’s effect on doctor retention in public hospitals has not been published, except for a study by Obianagwa et al. (2025) that utilised qualitative content analysis of secondary data. Policy documents describe the policy’s components and intent; however, academic records currently contain only commentaries, case syntheses, and descriptive reports rather than rigorous before-and-after or quasi-experimental evaluations of retention outcomes. This absence leaves policymakers without empirical evidence on whether NPHWM interventions are achieving measurable retention gains.

2.4.2 Local Context

National analyses and multi-state surveys provide important trend data, but they generally aggregate cadres and geographies. There is limited sub-national, facility-level evaluation of how the NPHWM has been operationalised in public hospitals, such as those in Edo State. Given the state's role as a hub for secondary and tertiary healthcare facilities, the lack of hospital-level implementation and outcome studies from Edo State constitutes a meso-level evidence gap that constrains context-sensitive policy refinement.

2.4.3 Policy Implementation

Existing empirical studies [for example, Onah et al., 2022; Badru et al., 2024] document strong physician migration intentions and identify push factors [poor pay, insecurity, inadequate facilities], but they do not assess post-policy awareness, access, or perceived effectiveness of NPHWM incentives among doctors. In short, there is little evidence at the doctor level on whether salary supplements, training pathways, return-readmission measures, or other NPHWM modalities are functioning as intended or influencing individual retention decisions. This micro-level lacuna impedes practical improvements to incentive design and uptake.

2.4.4 Policy Adoption and Adaptation

While international literature and regional case studies highlight potentially transferable mechanisms (e.g., bilateral labour agreements, skills partnerships, diaspora engagement models), Nigerian scholarship seldom evaluates these options empirically within Nigeria's fiscal and governance context. Without comparative assessments of how global best practices perform under Nigeria's institutional constraints, opportunities for adaptive policy learning remain underexploited. Regional reports and syntheses recommend such approaches, but empirical, Nigeria-focused testing is scarce.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

The theories of migration by Lee (1966) and motivation-hygiene by Herzberg (1966) will serve as the theoretical foundation for the assumptions and propositions concerning the relationships among the various concepts that will be studied in the present investigation.

2.5.1 Lee's Theory of Migration

The theory of migration by Lee (1966) conceptualises migration as a decision shaped by push-pull factors, intervening obstacles, and personal factors. Push factors in the current brain drain context are conditions at the place of origin that may prompt emigration; they include low pay, insecurity, inadequate infrastructure, and limited career progression opportunities. Pull factors, by contrast, are conditions at the destination country that have the potential to lure immigrants and include better remuneration, job security, advanced training opportunities, and structured work environments. Moreover, intervening obstacles are factors that mediate the actual emigration decision; they include immigration and legal restrictions, and migration processing fees that can either slow or accelerate migration flows. Finally, personal factors, or individual characteristics, such as the ability to perceive push, pull, and intervening obstacle factors, as well as amenability to change, are considerable roadblocks that need to be surmounted by the focal person involved [Figure 1]. In addition, Lee (1966) posited that migrations occurred in streams that are counterbalanced by migratory counterstreams [Figure 1].

The NPHWM interventions can be understood as a deliberate creation of institutional and/or individual obstacles to migration by offering incentives such as tax exemptions, credit facilities, bonuses, an adequate working environment, and security, as well as development opportunities to counterbalance the push and pull factors. Nonetheless, one could infer from Lee's migration theory that financial and non-financial incentives alone may still be insufficient to control outward movement, as the volume and rate of movement tend to increase over time, and the rationale for migration is not limited to the theoretical factors captured therein (Motadegbe & Mogaji, 2025).

Figure 3

An illustration of the Relationships of the Central Concepts in Lee's Theory of Migration.

Source: Principal investigator (2025)

2.5.2 Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory

Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory, also known as the Two-Factor Theory, emerged from Frederick Herzberg's research (1966) on job satisfaction and motivation. The theory posits that certain factors lead to positive attitudes towards work, while others lead to negative attitudes. Two major categories of factors were identified as affecting job satisfaction. The first category, motivators, is linked to the need for development and self-actualisation. Examples include achievement, recognition, the work itself, responsibility, advancement, and the possibility for growth. The second category, hygiene factors, is related to the need to avoid unpleasantness; examples include company policies and administration, relationships with supervisors,

interpersonal relations, working conditions, and salary. Hygiene factors are extrinsic to the job itself; their presence prevents dissatisfaction, but their absence leads to dissatisfaction. Motivators, on the other hand, are intrinsic factors linked to the nature of the work; they foster deep job satisfaction and long-term retention. The presence of motivators leads to job satisfaction, while their absence leads to dissatisfaction. In addition, a combination of high or low motivation factors with hygiene factors can produce one of four outcomes: high satisfaction, low satisfaction/neutral, a variable zone, and high dissatisfaction [Figure 1].

In healthcare, this theory has been particularly prominent. Some studies have shown that while improving pay and working conditions (hygiene factors) may reduce employee dissatisfaction, these factors alone cannot ensure loyalty or high morale (Alrawahi et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2017). Without motivators such as career development opportunities, respect within the workplace, and recognition of achievements, employees may remain disengaged and open to migration (Alrawahi et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2017). In the Nigerian context, hygiene factors are often chronically weak: hospitals frequently lack essential infrastructure, salaries may be delayed, and insecurity remains a persistent concern (Olowolaju et al., 2025). Even where motivators such as training opportunities exist, the negative impact of weak hygiene factors undermines their effect.

The NPHWM seeks to address both preceding factors by improving hygiene through financial allowances and housing initiatives, while also providing motivators in the form of expanded training and professional development opportunities. Nevertheless, Herzberg's framework suggests that unless both sets of factors are strengthened simultaneously, dissatisfaction will persist, and migration may remain an attractive option. This makes the theory highly relevant for analysing the policy's effectiveness in addressing the multi-layered reasons for workforce attrition.

Together, the preceding two theories, Lee's migration theory, and Herzberg's two-factor theory, provide a lens to examine the policy's capacity to alter migration-retention dynamics in Nigeria.

Figure 4

An illustration of the relationships of the central concepts in Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory.

Source: Principal investigator (2025)

2.6 Conclusion

The review of related literature underscores the persistent and multifaceted challenge of health workforce migration in Nigeria, particularly among doctors. Across global and national studies, common push factors, such as poor remuneration, weak health infrastructure, insecurity, and limited opportunities for career development, continue to dominate. Meanwhile, pull factors include better working conditions, structured training opportunities, and professional recognition abroad. Theoretical frameworks, such as Lee's migration theory and Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory, have been widely applied, offering helpful but often generalised explanations of migration drivers. Empirical studies within Nigeria consistently report high emigration intentions

among doctors and other healthcare workers; however, they remain primarily descriptive and national in focus, with limited disaggregation by cadre, facility type, or sub-national context.

Policy interventions, most notably the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM), constitute a significant federal response to curb “brain drain” through incentives, diaspora engagement, improved governance, and monitoring mechanisms such as the National Health Workforce Registry. However, the literature indicates that much of the scholarship to date remains conceptual or relies on secondary data, with very few empirical studies evaluating the NPHWM’s actual impact on retention outcomes. Furthermore, there is scant evidence from both urban and rural centres in Edo State, despite the presence of notable institutions of postgraduate medical training.

The gaps identified span multiple levels: at the macro level, there is a lack of empirical policy evaluation to determine whether the NPHWM has improved doctor retention; at the meso level, little is known about how public hospitals in Edo State implement or adapt policy directives; and at the micro level, doctors' perceptions and lived experiences of NPHWM incentives remain underexplored. Additionally, Nigerian scholarship has not sufficiently drawn lessons from comparative international practices, such as bilateral agreements and structured diaspora partnerships.

Given these gaps, the present study is both timely and necessary. By focusing on doctor retention in public hospitals in Edo State, it contributes original evidence to an under-researched sub-national context, evaluates the implementation of a recent and critical national policy, and amplifies doctor-level perspectives. In doing so, it provides policymakers with practical insights to refine retention strategies and offers a grounded evidence base to support Nigeria’s broader efforts to build a resilient health workforce.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Preamble

This chapter describes the methodological approach used to assess the impact of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM) on doctor retention in public hospitals in Edo State. It explains the research's philosophical orientation, the study population, the sampling methods, the instrument development and validation, and the analytical strategies used to interpret the data. Ethical issues guiding the study are also discussed.

3.2 Research Philosophy

The research was primarily anchored in the pragmatic philosophical paradigm, which emphasises the use of all possible approaches to understand a problem (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). Pragmatism focuses on actions, situations, and consequences rather than antecedent conditions. This philosophy is appropriate for the present study because it is real-world oriented, problem-centred, and pluralistic. It allows the researcher to examine cause-and-effect relationships between variables, specifically, the influence of the NPHWM on doctor retention rates, using empirical data from public hospitals, while also capturing detailed insights from respondents through open-ended recommendations or suggestions.

3.3 Research Design

The study employed a quasi-convergent mixed methods design, combining a quantitative survey with a qualitative descriptive approach (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). This design involves collecting both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently from a defined population to examine the relationships between policy awareness, interventions, and retention outcomes. It is well-suited for this study as it enables systematic measurement of doctors' awareness and perceptions of the NPHWM, assessment of the self-reported impact of NPHWM interventions on doctor retention,

and collection of open-ended recommendations for policy improvement. By providing a dual perspective, the design captures a comprehensive snapshot of the current situation while allowing for statistical comparisons across demographic and institutional groups.

3.4 Population/Area of the Study

The study was conducted among thirty-three public secondary healthcare facilities in Edo State and a tertiary facility at its centre. The state is an inland state in southern Nigeria, bordered by Kogi, Anambra, Delta, Ondo, and the Niger River [Figure 5] (Britannica Editors, 2025).

Benin City, situated at 6°26'N and 5°41'E (Ben-Amos, 2018), serves as the capital of Edo State and is renowned for its historical significance involving 'bronze' or rather brass work dating back to the 13th century.

The study population, eight hundred and fifteen [815], will comprise all medical doctors and dental surgeons working across the thirty-three secondary hospitals under the Edo State Hospitals Management Agency and the University of Benin Teaching Hospital. This population included consultants, resident doctors, and medical and dental officers who had served for at least one year in their current institution.

Figure 5

Map of Edo State

Source: United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs [OCHA], 2018.

3.5 Sample Size and Sampling Techniques / Exclusion and Inclusion Criteria

3.5.1 Sample Size Determination

Sample size calculation was undertaken using the G*Power software (version 3.1.9.7) by Faul et al. (2009). Sample size calculation using G*Power version 3.1.9.7 will be carried out using the following parameter values, if the sample has a normal distribution:

- Tails = two
- Correlation $\rho H_1 = 0.50$
- Level of significance, $\alpha = 0.05$
- Power, $1 - \beta = 80\%$
- Correlation $\rho H_0 = 0.25$

The minimum required sample size = 93.

Figure 6

*G*Power Sample Size Calculation.*

Because the population of this study was finite, the formula:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{(n_0 - 1)}{N}}$$

[finite population correction factor] would have been applied to adjust the sample size. However, since the minimum sample size required [93] is barely 11.4% of the study population, the correction factor was not applied to make allowance for non-responses. In addition, a sample size of one hundred and twelve [112], which is greater than the minimum required sample size of ninety-three, was used for this study.

3.5.2 Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling approach was adopted for this study.

Stage 1: A purposive selection was conducted to include all 33 secondary hospitals under the Edo State Hospitals Management Agency, as well as the University of Benin Teaching Hospital. These facilities were selected based on their relevance to the study population and their roles as major centres of care delivery within the state.

Stage 2: Sampling units were then selected from the identified hospital categories in relation to their population sizes. This ensured adequate representation across facilities with varying patient volumes and staff strength.

Stage 3: Eligible respondents within the selected units were recruited using convenience sampling through official hospital WhatsApp groups. This approach is necessitated by the inability to obtain ethical clearance for access to personal contact information on the hospital register, which precluded the use of simple random sampling. Although the use of convenience sampling may introduce selection bias, deliberate measures were adopted to minimise its potential effects. These included ensuring wide circulation of the survey link across all hospital WhatsApp groups at different times of the day, complemented by bulk messaging to individual group members; the use of bulk SMS to reach potential respondents via their phone numbers; and maintaining an extended data collection period to accommodate varying staff schedules and duty rosters.

$$\text{Sampling fraction} = \frac{\text{Sample size } (n)}{\text{Sample frame } (N)} = \frac{112}{815} = 0.137$$

Number of sampling units = sampling fraction × doctor population [Table 1].

Table 1

Proportional Allocation of Sampling Units to Tertiary and Secondary Hospitals.

Hospital Type	Doctor Population	Sampling Fraction	Number of Sampling Units Required
Tertiary [UBTH]	600	0.137	82
Secondary [Hospitals under Edo State HMA]	215	0.137	30
Total	815		112

*UBTH: University of Benin Teaching Hospital; HMA: Hospitals Management Agency.

3.5.3 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

3.5.3.1 Inclusion Criteria

- i. Doctors who have worked in the UBTH or a secondary healthcare facility under the Edo State HMA for at least 12 consecutive months.
- ii. Doctors on permanent employment with their respective hospitals.
- iii. Doctors who consented to participate in the present study.

3.5.3.2 Exclusion Criteria

- i. Doctors working for a public primary healthcare facility, a private primary, secondary, or tertiary healthcare facility, a neuropsychiatric hospital, a military hospital, or any tertiary healthcare facility that is not UBTH.

- ii. Doctors who have not worked in the UBTH and secondary healthcare facilities under the Edo state HMA for not up to 12 consecutive months.
- iii. House officers, Corper doctors, locum physicians, and dentists.
- iv. Doctors who are on long-term study leave or unavailable during data collection.
- v. Respondents who decline to give consent.

3.6 Research Instrument

The main research instrument will be a structured, self-administered questionnaire designed by the principal investigator based on the study's objectives and the literature review findings. The instrument comprises four sections:

- **Section A:** Socio-demographic data [age, gender, cadre, years of service, and institution].
- **Section B:** Awareness and perception of doctors on the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration.
- **Section C:** Assessment of NPHWM interventions [incentives, welfare, professional development, and migration control measures].
- **Section D:** Doctor retention and intention to migrate.
- **Section E:** Suggestions and recommendations

All items were rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from *Strongly Agree (5)* to *Strongly Disagree (1)* to quantify respondents' opinions.

3.7 Validity and Reliability of Instrument

3.7.1 Validity

The research instrument will undergo a comprehensive validation process, including an expert review by a public policy specialist and the project supervisor to assess face and content validity.

3.7.2 Reliability

A pilot test was conducted with 17 doctors from government hospitals outside Edo State to evaluate the internal consistency of the items in the study instrument. Data from the pilot was analysed using the Cronbach's α method; a value of 0.955 was obtained after analysis [Appendix III].

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

Quantitative data were cleaned, processed, and analysed using IBM® SPSS® Statistics version 20 (IBM Corp., 2011), while qualitative data were analysed using the RQDA package version 0.3 (Huang, 2018) within the R software (version 3.6.1) environment. The analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means or medians, and standard deviations or interquartile ranges, were used to summarise socio-demographic characteristics, awareness and perception, and policy intervention domains.

Questionnaire responses were scored according to a Likert scale, with higher scores indicating greater awareness, more positive perceptions, or stronger agreement with policy intervention effectiveness. Domain scores were computed by summing individual item responses within each section, allowing for an overall assessment of awareness, perception, and policy intervention domains. Normality testing was not conducted because the variables of interest were measured on an ordinal (Likert) scale; therefore, non-parametric tests were applied.

Descriptive statistics, including mean, median, standard deviation, and interquartile range, were used to compare pre-policy and post-policy doctor retention data. Spearman correlation and binary logistic regression analyses were conducted to assess the strength and direction of relationships between policy interventions and retention outcomes. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

3.9 Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance was sought and obtained [**Approval number: HA/737/25/C/12011023**] from the Edo State Ministry of Health Research Ethics Committee [Appendix IV]. Respondents

were informed of the study's purpose, assured of confidentiality, and provided with consent forms indicating voluntary participation. Personal identifiers were excluded to ensure anonymity, and participants retained the right to withdraw from the study at any point without penalty. The research strictly adhered to the ethical principles of autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice throughout its execution.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Preamble

This chapter presents the main findings of this study, providing a structured review of the collected data. It begins by explaining how the data is displayed, then presents a detailed analysis to identify meaningful patterns and insights related to the research objectives. The chapter then tests the formulated hypothesis and compares it with the research propositions, assessing how well the findings support or contradict the expected outcomes. Finally, it concludes with a summary of the key findings.

4.2 Data Presentation

4.2.1 Respondents' Socio-demographics

Table 2 summarises the socio-demographic characteristics of the 112 respondents. The mean and median ages were 39.23 (SD = 5.20) and 40.00 (IQR = 10.75) years, respectively. The majority (90, 80.4%) were male, and 22 (19.6%) were female. Most respondents were married (84, 75%) and held MBBS/BDS qualifications (82, 73.2%). In terms of cadre, most respondents were Residents (82, 73.2%), with fewer Consultants (16, 14.3%), Dental Officers (4, 3.6%), and Medical Officers (10, 8.9%). All respondents (112, 100%) had been in their current employment for more than 12 months, and 50% had 1–5 years of professional service. More than four-fifths of respondents (96, 85.7%) worked at UBTH.

Table 2*Socio-Demographic Information of the Study Respondents (n =112)*

Variable	Category	Frequency (%)
Age (years)	Mean (SD)	39.23 (5.20) *
	Median (IQR)	40.00 (10.75) **
Gender	Male	90 (80.4)
	Female	22 (19.6)
Civil state	Married	84 (75.0)
	Single	28 (25.0)
Highest qualification	MBBS/BDS	82 (73.2)
	Fellowship	20 (17.9)
	Master's	8 (7.1)
	PhD	2 (1.8)
Cadre	Resident	82 (73.2)
	Consultant	16 (14.3)
	Dental Officer	4 (3.6)
	Medical Officer	10 (8.9)
Duration of current employment	> 12 months	112 (100.0)
	< 12 months	0 (0.0)
Years in Professional Service	1–5 years	56 (50.0)
	6–10 years	34 (30.4)
	11–15 years	12 (10.7)
	> 15 years	10 (8.9)
Respondents' Facility	UBTH	96 (85.7)
	Edo State HMA	16 (14.3)

*SD: Standard Deviation; **IQR: Inter-quartile Range

4.2.2 Awareness and Perception of Respondents to NPHWM

Regarding respondents' awareness of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM), 74 respondents (66.1%) reported being unaware of the policy, whereas slightly over one-third, 38 (33.9%), indicated awareness of its existence. Respondents' awareness and perception scores, measured on a scale with a maximum attainable score of 40, had a mean of 17.34 (SD = 5.28) and a median of 18.00 (IQR = 7.00) [Table 5].

4.2.3 NPHWM Interventions

Mean and median scores for the assessed policy intervention domains, out of a maximum attainable score of 25, are presented as follows. The incentives and welfare domain recorded a mean of 8.50 (SD = 4.40) and a median of 7.00 (IQR = 6.00). Capacity building and professional development had a higher central tendency, with a mean of 11.77 (SD = 4.19) and a median of 12.00 (IQR = 5.00). Similarly, digital health and technology integration yielded a mean of 11.48 (SD = 4.50) and a median of 12.00 (IQR = 7.75). Work–life balance, wellbeing, and safety recorded a mean of 9.52 (SD = 3.81) and a median of 9.50 (IQR = 6.00). The return, readmission, and diaspora engagement domain had a mean of 10.61 (SD = 3.02) and a median of 10.00 (IQR = 3.00). International collaboration and ethical recruitment recorded a mean of 11.38 (SD = 4.05) and a median of 12.00 (IQR = 7.50). Finally, rural and underserved area support recorded comparatively lower scores, with a mean of 8.96 (SD = 4.41) and a median of 8.00 (IQR = 6.00) [Table 5].

4.2.4 Doctor Retention and Intention to Migrate

On a maximum score of 31, the doctor retention and intention to migrate scale recorded a mean of 11.38 (SD = 4.55) and a median of 11.50 (IQR = 7.00) [Table 5]. On dichotomising the doctor retention and intention to migrate scale by score, the majority (92, 82.1%) were more amenable to migrating, compared with the smaller group (20, 17.9%) who were more open to remaining in employment and in Nigeria.

Table 3*Descriptive Statistics of Awareness, NPHWM Interventions, and Doctor Retention Outcomes*

Variable	Maximum Score	Mean	SD	Median	IQR
<i>Awareness and Perception of NPHWM</i>	40	17.34	5.28	18.00	7.00
<i>Incentives and Welfare</i>	25	8.50	4.40	7.00	6.00
<i>Capacity Building and Development</i>	25	11.77	4.19	12.00	5.00
<i>Digital Health and Technology Integration</i>	25	11.48	4.50	12.00	7.75
<i>Work–Life Balance, Wellbeing, and Safety</i>	25	9.52	3.81	9.50	6.00
<i>Return, Readmission, and Diaspora Engagement</i>	25	10.61	3.02	10.00	3.00
<i>International Collaboration and Ethical Recruitment</i>	25	11.38	4.05	12.00	7.50
<i>Rural and Underserved Area Support</i>	25	8.96	4.41	8.00	6.00
<i>Doctor Retention and Intention to Migrate</i>	31	11.38	4.55	11.50	7.00

SD: Standard deviation; IQR: Inter-quartile range

4.3 Data Analysis

4.3.1 Research Question 1

How do annual retention rates of doctors in selected public hospitals compare between the pre-NPHWM period (2022 – 2023) and the post-NPHWM period (2024 – 2025)?

Employment figures for doctors reveal distinct and contrasting trends between the University of Benin Teaching Hospital (UBTH) and the Edo State Hospitals Management Agency (HMA) between 2022 and 2025. At UBTH, employment patterns indicate a generally concerning contraction of the medical workforce over the study period, although there are signs of recent stabilisation. The number of employed doctors declined from a baseline of 706 in 2022 to 579 in

2023, before recovering to a projected 600 doctors in 2025 (UBTH, 2025). The most pronounced reduction occurred between 2022 (706) and 2023 (579), representing a 17.99% decline within a single year, largely preceding the activation of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM). While the introduction of the NPHWM in 2024 did not immediately reverse workforce losses, it coincided with a moderation of the downward trend. The rate of decline slowed to 3.63% between 2023 and 2024, followed by a 7.52% increase in retention between 2024 and 2025, reflecting a modest rebound in doctor numbers.

A comparison of net retention rates before and after the implementation of the NPHWM further highlights this shift. Whereas a substantial 17.99% decrease was recorded in the pre-policy period (2022–2023), the post-policy period (2024–2025) shows a positive retention rate, with a 3.89% increase.

Table 4

UBTH Employment and Annual Retention Rate (2022–2025)

Year	Number of Doctors [UBTH]	Mean	Annual Retention Rate (%)
2022	706	Pre-NPHWM ≈ 643	NA
2023	579		↓ 17.99%
2024	558	Post-NPHWM 579	↓ 3.63%
2025	600		↑ 7.52%

*UBTH: University of Benin Teaching Hospital

Employment figures for the Edo State Hospitals Management Agency (HMA) are highly volatile, with pronounced year-to-year fluctuations throughout the study period. This instability is particularly noteworthy given that the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM) was designed to reduce such variability through improved welfare provisions and working conditions.

Three distinct phases are evident. First, during the pre-policy period (2022–2023), the HMA recorded a substantial surge in employment, with doctor numbers rising from 172 to 236, representing a 37.21% increase. Second, this expansion was abruptly reversed during the policy intervention phase (2023–2024), when employment fell sharply from 236 to 189, a 19.92% decline (Edo State Hospital Management Agency, 2025). Notably, this period of pronounced attrition coincided with the anticipated commencement and early implementation of the NPHWM in 2024, suggesting a limited immediate policy effect. Finally, the post-contraction period (2024–2025) was characterised by a rapid rebound, as employment rose from 189 to 215, corresponding to a 13.76% increase.

A comparison of net retention rates before and after the implementation of the NPHWM further reinforces this pattern, with a 37.21% increase observed in 2022–2023, contrasted with a notable 6.16% decline in 2024–2025.

Table 5

Edo State HMA Doctor Employment and Annual Retention Rate (2022–2025)

Year	Number of Doctors [HMA]	Mean	Annual Retention Rate (%)
2022	172	Pre-NPHWM 204	NA
2023	236		↑ 37.21%
2024	189	Post-NPHWM 202	↓ 19.92%
2025	215		↑ 13.76%

*HMA: Edo State Hospital Management Agency.

4.3.2 Research Question 2

What is the strength of the association between each core NPHWM intervention and doctors' decisions to remain in public service?

On computing Spearman's correlation analysis between the following variables: incentives and welfare, capacity building and development, digital health and technology integration, work–life balance, wellbeing and safety, return, readmission, and diaspora engagement, international collaboration and ethical recruitment, rural and underserved area support, awareness and perception of the policy, and the doctor's decision to remain in public service, all interventions, including incentives and welfare ($\rho = 0.39$; < 0.01), capacity building and development ($\rho = 0.42$; < 0.01), digital health and technology integration ($\rho = 0.39$; < 0.01), work–life balance, wellbeing and safety ($\rho = 0.53$; < 0.01), return, readmission, and diaspora engagement ($\rho = 0.32$; < 0.01), international collaboration and ethical recruitment ($\rho = 0.47$; < 0.01), rural and underserved area support ($\rho = 0.32$; < 0.01), were noted to positively increase in magnitude as the doctor's decision to remain in public service increased. In addition, doctors' awareness and perception of the policy also increased in magnitude as their likelihood to remain in service increased ($\rho = 0.44$; < 0.001).

The strength of the association between the above NPHWM interventions and doctors' retention decision ranges from moderate to strong, in line with Quinnipiac University's interpretation of Spearman's correlation coefficient (Akoglu, 2018).

4.3.3 Research Question 3

What actionable strategies and policy refinements can be recommended to enhance the effectiveness of the NPHWM in improving retention based on the present study?

A thematic analysis of respondents' suggestions and recommendations regarding the policy was conducted. Key themes identified included the need for clear government intentions and sincerity in improving welfare and implementing policies effectively; the formulation of specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) policies, with regular review and updates informed by adequate stakeholder engagement; increased awareness of the policy,

4.4 Hypotheses Testing/Juxtaposition of Research Proposition

H₀ 1: There is no statistically significant relationship between any NPHWM intervention and doctors' decisions to remain in public service.

H_a 1: There is a statistically significant relationship between at least one NPHWM intervention and doctors' decisions to remain in public service.

A binary logistic regression analysis was conducted to examine whether the core interventions of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM) significantly predicted doctors' retention decisions, as reported by the study respondents. The predictors included in the model were incentives and welfare, capacity building and development, digital health and technology integration, work–life balance, wellbeing and safety, return, readmission, diaspora engagement, international collaboration and ethical recruitment, rural and underserved area support, and awareness and perception of the policy.

The overall logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2 (7) = 28.90$, $p = 0.006$, indicating that the predictors collectively distinguished between doctors who remained in employment and those who did not. The model explained between 22.7% (Cox & Snell R^2) and 37.4% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in doctor retention outcomes.

The Hosmer–Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 70.11$, $p < 0.001$), indicating some discrepancy between observed and predicted probabilities. However, this test is known to be sensitive to sample size. Other diagnostic indicators, including the significant Omnibus test and the magnitude of the pseudo- R^2 values, indicate that the model retains adequate explanatory utility.

At the individual predictor level, international collaboration and ethical recruitment significantly predicted doctors' retention decisions (OR = 1.37, 95% CI: 1.05–1.80, $p = 0.03$). Awareness and perception of the policy also emerged as a significant predictor (OR = 1.26, 95% CI: 1.06–1.49, $p = 0.01$).

The remaining intervention domains did not significantly predict doctor retention: incentives and welfare (OR = 0.89, 95% CI: 0.70–1.13, $p > 0.05$), capacity building and development (OR = 0.90, 95% CI: 0.70–1.14, $p > 0.05$), digital health and technology integration (OR = 0.84, 95% CI: 0.68–1.02, $p > 0.05$), work–life balance, wellbeing and safety (OR = 1.19, 95% CI: 0.91–1.56, $p > 0.05$), return, readmission, and diaspora engagement (OR = 0.87, 95% CI: 0.63–1.21, $p > 0.05$), and rural and underserved area support (OR = 1.11, 95% CI: 0.92–1.35, $p > 0.05$) [Table 6].

Given that at least one NPHWM policy intervention, specifically international collaboration and ethical recruitment, was a statistically significant predictor of doctors' retention, the null hypothesis (H_0 1), which states that there is no statistically significant relationship between any NPHWM intervention and doctors' decisions to remain in public service, can be rejected, and the alternative hypothesis that specific NPHWM interventions are associated with doctors' decisions to remain in public service can be accepted.

Table 6*Binary Logistic Regression Predicting Doctor Retention*

Predictor	B	SE	Wald	df	p-value (Sig.)	Exp(B)	95% CI for Exp(B)
<i>Incentives and Welfare</i>	-0.116	0.121	0.924	1	0.336	0.891	0.703 – 1.128
<i>Capacity Building and Development</i>	-0.107	0.124	0.738	1	0.390	0.899	0.704 – 1.147
<i>Digital Health and Technology Integration</i>	-0.178	0.103	3.006	1	0.083	0.837	0.684 – 1.024
<i>Work–Life Balance, Wellbeing, and Safety</i>	0.171	0.138	1.537	1	0.215	1.187	0.905 – 1.556
<i>Return, Readmission, and Diaspora Engagement</i>	-0.138	0.170	0.666	1	0.415	0.871	0.625 – 1.214
<i>International Collaboration and Ethical Recruitment</i>	0.318	0.139	5.227	1	0.022	1.374	1.046 – 1.804
<i>Rural and Underserved Area Support</i>	0.107	0.099	1.170	1	0.279	1.113	0.917 – 1.350
<i>Awareness and Perception</i>	0.231	0.087	7.056	1	0.008	1.260	1.062 – 1.494
<i>Constant</i>	-6.822	1.805	14.279	1	0.000	0.001	–

4.5 Summary of Findings

This chapter presented and analysed the study’s findings on the impact of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM) on doctor retention rates in selected public hospitals in Edo State. The chapter commenced with a description of respondents’ socio-demographic characteristics, revealing a predominantly male, married, and resident doctor workforce, with most respondents having several years of professional experience and being primarily employed at the University of Benin Teaching Hospital (UBTH).

Findings on awareness of the NPHWM showed generally low policy visibility, with approximately two-thirds of respondents unaware of the policy. Correspondingly, awareness and perception scores were below optimal levels. Descriptive analysis of the NPHWM interventions showed moderate performance across most intervention areas, with relatively higher scores in capacity building, digital health integration, and international collaboration, and lower scores in incentives, welfare, and rural support.

Analysis of doctor retention outcomes indicated a strong inclination to migrate, with over four-fifths of respondents more likely to leave public service than to remain. A comparison of pre- and post-NPHWM retention trends showed contrasting patterns across institutions. At UBTH, a sharp decline in doctor numbers occurred before policy implementation, followed by a slowdown in attrition and a modest post-policy recovery. In contrast, employment trends under the Edo State Hospitals Management Agency (HMA) were highly volatile, with substantial fluctuations before and after policy implementation, suggesting limited immediate stabilising effects of the NPHWM.

Correlation analysis showed statistically significant positive associations between all NPHWM interventions and doctors' decisions to remain in public service, with effect sizes ranging from moderate to strong. Awareness and perception of the policy also showed a significant positive relationship with retention intentions.

Binary logistic regression analysis further revealed that, although the overall model significantly predicted doctors' retention decisions, only international collaboration, ethical recruitment, and awareness and perception of the policy emerged as significant independent predictors. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming that at least one NPHWM intervention significantly influences doctors' decisions to remain in public service.

Finally, thematic analysis of respondents' recommendations highlighted the need for stronger government commitment, better-designed and regularly reviewed policies, increased policy awareness, decentralised implementation, structured migration management, staff replacement strategies, infrastructure improvements, enhanced welfare, and improved remuneration. Together, these findings provide empirical evidence of the partial effectiveness of the NPHWM and underscore critical gaps that require policy refinement to strengthen doctor retention.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

5.1 Preamble

This chapter serves as an analytical bridge, moving beyond raw statistics to explain the *why* behind doctor retention trends in Edo State, Nigeria. By triangulating empirical data with Lee's Migration Theory and Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, the chapter investigates the socio-political nuances of the *Japa* phenomenon. It specifically examines the divergence between federal and state institutional performance and the hierarchy of motivators for doctors. Ultimately, the goal of this section is to provide a diagnostic lens for re-evaluating the NPHWM as a functional, real-world intervention rather than a mere administrative directive.

5.2 Sociodemographics of Respondents

The study found that the average age of respondents was 39–40 years, as expected given that house officers and corper doctors were excluded. Four out of every five respondents were male, possibly reflecting a higher male presence on WhatsApp within the studied hospitals. Similarly, four out of five respondents held a bachelor's degree, were married, and were resident doctors. Half of respondents had less than six years of professional experience and were affiliated with UBTH.

5.3 Policy Visibility and the Information Asymmetry

A central finding of this study is the information asymmetry surrounding the NPHWM. Despite its launch in August 2024 by the Federal Ministry of Health and Social Welfare, 66.1% of respondents remained unaware of the policy's specific provisions (see Table 5). In public policy theory, an intervention's efficacy depends largely on its communicative power (Kondolele et al., 2025). If practitioners are unaware of incentives such as tax holidays, exchange programmes, mortgage facilities, or the one-to-one replacement for staff turnover, these factors cannot influence their rational decision to migrate. This finding suggests a significant failure in effective policy dissemination. As Nwankwo (2023) notes, Nigerian health policies frequently suffer from poor sensitisation of frontline workers. The fact that only 33.9% of the 112 studied doctors were aware

of the policy underscores a disconnect between federal rhetoric and facility-level reality. As emphasised by Hudson et al. (2019), policy intentions often falter at the ground level without active monitoring and stakeholder engagement. Our data imply that the stewardship and engagement goals highlighted in the NPHWM document have not yet reached the clinical frontline in Edo State, explaining why six out of seven policy interventions showed no statistically significant effect on doctor retention (see Table 6).

5.4 Institutional Divergence and Retention Trends

The longitudinal analysis reveals a stark divergence between federal and state healthcare institutions. At the University of Benin Teaching Hospital (UBTH), the data show a modest 3.89% increase in the retention rate in the post-policy period (2024–2025), reversing a sharp decline from previous years. This recovery suggests that federal tertiary institutions, which are closely aligned with national budgetary priorities, are experiencing early-stage policy signalling effects.

Conversely, the hospitals under the Edo State Hospitals Management Agency (HMA) experienced a 6.16% decline in the retention rate during the same period. This underscores a decentralisation bottleneck, with state-level facilities facing fragmented funding and remunerative disparities compared with their federal counterparts. This institutional disparity is further evidenced by 2025 reports of warning strikes in Edo State, where resident doctors cited poor pay relative to federal colleagues as a primary driver of continued attrition (The Nigerian Observer, 2025). In sum, the NPHWM has not yet yielded measurable retention gains across the board; the continued attrition observed is consistent with the report by Kola (2023), which noted that over 5,000 Nigerian doctors had migrated to the UK within a five-year window.

5.5 The Hierarchy of Retention Motivators: Theory vs. Practice

The study identifies a clear hierarchy of what motivates a doctor to remain in public service. Spearman’s correlation analysis indicated that work-life balance, wellbeing, and safety ($\rho = 0.53$) were the strongest correlates of a doctor’s desire to remain in service. This confirms Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory, identifying personal safety and manageable workloads as critical hygiene

factors, those whose absence causes dissatisfaction but whose presence alone may not ensure long-term retention (Herzberg, 1966).

However, the binary logistic regression analysis provided the most robust diagnosis, showing that while safety makes doctors happier, international collaboration and ethical recruitment (OR = 1.37) and policy awareness (OR = 1.26) are the only significant independent predictors of the decision to stay. The findings showed that doctors were 37% and 26% more likely to migrate when policy emphasised international collaboration, ethical recruitment, and awareness. This also suggests that for a doctor to forgo migration, they require more than perceiving a tangible, transparent professional path facilitated by ethical global standards. Other contributing factors, such as incentives and welfare, and enhanced career pathways, for example, must also be addressed, which is in line with Lee's migration theory's inference that non-financial incentives alone cannot prevent migratory movements.

The dissatisfaction with current incentives is evident in the data: the mean and median scores for *incentives and welfare* were 8.5 and 7 out of a maximum of 25 (see Table 5). This low score indicates that the coordinated reforms called for by the World Health Organisation (2010) regarding remuneration and working conditions have not yet materialised for doctors in Edo State.

5.6 The *Japa* Phenomenon as a Rational Response

The findings from this study highlight that the NPHWM is currently struggling to serve as the *intervening obstacle* proposed by Lee's Migration Theory (Lee, 1966). Despite incentives such as rural posting allowances and digital technology integration, the *push factors* remain overwhelming. In 2024 alone, 4,193 doctors and dentists left Nigeria (Hardball, 2025). The study's results show that financial constraints, specifically Nigeria allocating only 5.15% of its budget to health in 2025, far below the 15% Abuja Declaration target, severely limit the reach of NPHWM welfare packages (Development Research and Projects Centre, 2025).

In addition, our thematic analysis of respondents' suggestions indicates that for the policy to be effective, there must be a shift towards apparent government sincerity and the formulation of SMART policies, supported by regular stakeholder engagement, increased awareness, and robust monitoring mechanisms. There is a need to domesticate interventions at the state level, ensure the

timely replacement of departing staff to reduce burnout, and implement comprehensive infrastructural reforms alongside enhanced remuneration through regular salary and allowance increments. As evidenced by the word cloud analysis, terms such as implementation, welfare, and improvement emerged as the most frequent concerns. The NPHWM currently exists mainly on paper; without a bridge between policy and practice, the Japa syndrome will remain the rational professional choice for Nigerian doctors facing the superior pull factors of destination countries such as the US and UK.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Preamble

This concluding chapter provides a sum-up of this research enquiry, which sought to assess the impact of the national policy on health workforce migration [NPHWM] on doctor retention rates in public hospitals in Edo state, Nigeria. This chapter summarises the key findings, draws definitive conclusions, and offers evidence-based recommendations aimed at bridging the *implementation-perception gap* that currently facilitates the systemic bleeding of Nigeria's medical human capital.

6.2 Summary

This study's assessment of the NPHWM's impact on doctor retention in Edo State reveals a detailed policy environment characterised by a pronounced gap between policy intent, awareness, and practical effect. Analysis of primary data from 112 medical practitioners indicates that the Japa phenomenon remains pervasive, with 82.1% of respondents more inclined to migrate abroad despite the introduction of the policy. This persistent migration intention appears to be reinforced by limited institutional penetration of the NPHWM, as 66.1% of respondents reported no awareness of the policy or its specific provisions, including welfare-related incentives.

Trend analysis further demonstrates mixed institutional outcomes following policy implementation. While the University of Benin Teaching Hospital (UBTH) recorded a modest post-policy improvement in doctor retention, with a net increase of 3.89%, employment patterns within the Edo State Hospitals Management Agency (HMA) remained unstable, marked by continued fluctuations and an overall decline in staffing levels. These divergent patterns suggest uneven policy uptake and implementation across public health institutions.

Inferential analyses provide additional insight into the mechanisms influencing retention. Although work-life balance, wellbeing, and safety showed the strongest positive association with doctors' willingness to remain in public service ($p = 0.53$), binary logistic regression analysis

identified awareness of and perceptions of the policy, alongside international collaboration and ethical recruitment frameworks, as the only statistically significant independent predictors of actual retention decisions. Collectively, these findings suggest that, while the NPHWM is conceptually robust, its limited visibility, uneven domestication, and weak institutional embedding have constrained its capacity to meaningfully counteract the ongoing medical workforce outflow.

6.3 Conclusion

The study concludes that the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration is a significant but currently underperforming effort to stabilise the Nigerian health workforce. While the policy contains the theoretical levers needed to address migration, its practical efficacy in Edo State is undermined by poor communication and inconsistent adoption across the tiers of healthcare. Rejecting the null hypothesis confirms that policy interventions can influence retention; however, the alarming 82.1% decision to migrate suggests that the policy has not yet fundamentally altered the push-pull relationship for the average practitioner. Ultimately, until the NPHWM is transformed from a federal directive into a tangible, visible reality at the facility level, addressing both hygiene factors, such as improved remuneration, and motivators, such as professional growth, the Nigerian public health sector will continue to serve as a training ground for the global medical market.

6.4 Recommendations

Based on the empirical findings and the identified implementation gaps, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. *Aggressive Policy Marketing and Sensitisation:* The Federal and State Ministries of Health must move from policy formulation to active policy marketing. Targeted sensitisation workshops should be held in every public hospital to ensure that practitioners are aware of the specific incentives, such as the 1-to-1 replacement rule and rural posting allowances.
- ii. *State-Level Domestication of the NPHWM:* The Edo State Government should immediately domesticate the national framework by establishing a state-level health workforce migration unit. This would ensure that state-managed hospitals receive the same level of funding, oversight, and recruitment priority as federal tertiary institutions.

- iii. *Prioritisation of Ethical Migration Frameworks*: Given that international collaboration and ethical recruitment were the primary predictors of retention, the government should prioritise bilateral skills partnerships. These agreements should enable regulated, circular migration, with destination countries investing in Nigeria's local training infrastructure in exchange for temporary recruitment.
- iv. *Institutionalising Wellbeing and Safety Protocols*: To address the strongest correlate of retention ($\rho = 0.53$), hospital management must implement rigorous safety protocols and flexible working-hour initiatives to combat burnout, which fuels the desire to migrate.

6.5 Contributions to Knowledge

- i. *Empirical Baseline for Policy Evaluation*: This study presents the first facility-level impact assessment of the NPHWM in Edo State since its official launch in August 2024, providing a real-time diagnostic for policymakers.
- ii. *Identification of Awareness as a Predictor*: Moving beyond traditional economic arguments, this research empirically demonstrates that *policy awareness* is a statistically significant predictor of doctor retention, highlighting the role of *information asymmetry* in policy failure.
- iii. *Validation of Theoretical Frameworks*: The study successfully validates the relevance of Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory and Lee's Migration Theory in the contemporary Nigerian context.

6.6 Limitations of the Study

- i. *Geographic Scope*: The study focused exclusively on Edo State, which may limit the generalisability of the findings to other regions with different fiscal capacities or migration patterns.
- ii. *Sampling*: The use of a non-probability sampling technique, due to the absence of a sample frame, while sufficient for statistical significance, may not fully capture the diverse perspectives of the entire Edo medical community.

- iii. *Temporal Constraint:* As the NPHWM is a relatively recent intervention [launched in late 2024], the study captures early-stage implementation data that may evolve as the policy matures.

6.7 Suggestions for Further Research

- i. *Longitudinal Migration Tracking:* A five-year longitudinal study is recommended to track the 2025 cohort of doctors, comparing intended migration with actual migration to assess the long-term effectiveness of policy incentives.
- ii. *Comparative Regional Analysis:* Future research should compare the impact of the NPHWM in states with higher healthcare investment (e.g., Lagos) with that in states with lower healthcare funding to identify the role of sub-national fiscal health in policy success.
- iii. *Qualitative Analysis of Returnees:* A qualitative study of doctors who have returned to Nigeria through the NPHWM's *return and reintegration* programme would provide deep insights into the most effective pull factors for brain gain.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I

Research Consent Form

Research Title:

Assessment of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM) and Doctor Retention in Public Hospitals in Edo State, Nigeria

Introduction

You are being invited to participate in a research study assessing the implementation and impact of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM) and how it affects doctor retention in Edo State. Please read the information below before deciding whether to participate.

Purpose of the Study

The study aims to assess doctors' awareness and perception of the NPHWM, evaluate key interventions introduced by the policy, and determine how these interventions influence retention and migration decisions.

What Participation Involves

You will complete a short questionnaire that takes about *10–15 minutes*. No personal identifiers will be collected, and there are no physical procedures involved.

Voluntary Participation

Participation is entirely voluntary. You may withdraw at any time by exiting the form, and you may skip any question you are not comfortable answering. There are no penalties or consequences for choosing not to participate.

Potential Risks

The risks are minimal. Some questions may cause mild discomfort if they relate to workplace experiences or personal plans, but you may skip any such item.

Benefits

Although you may not directly benefit, your responses will contribute to improving doctor retention strategies, policy implementation, and strengthening the Nigerian health workforce.

Confidentiality

Your responses will remain **anonymous**. No names, emails, or personal identifiers will be collected. All data will be stored securely and used for research purposes only.

Participant Signature

Date

Appendix II
QUESTIONNAIRE

Assessment of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM)

SECTION A: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

1. **Age (in years):** _____
2. **Gender:** Male Female
3. **Marital Status:** Single Married Divorced/Widowed
4. **Highest Qualification:** MBBS BDS Fellowship MPH MSc/PhD Others
(specify) _____
5. **Cadre/Rank:** Dental Officer Medical Officer Resident Doctor Consultant
6. **Years in Service:** 1–5 6–10 11–15 16 and above
7. **Name of Institution:** UBTH A Hospital under the Edo HMA
8. **Employment Type:** Full-time Contract Visiting
9. **Duration of Current Employment (in months)?** < 12 months ≥ 12 months
10. **Are you aware of the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (NPHWM)?**
 Yes No

SECTION B: AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION OF THE NPHWM

Instruction: Tick (✓) the option that best represents your view.

Scale: 5 – Strongly Agree 4 – Agree 3 – Undecided 2 – Disagree 1 – Strongly Disagree

1. I am familiar with the objectives of the NPHWM. 5 4 3 2 1

2. The policy was adequately communicated to health professionals in my institution. 5 4
3 2 1
3. I understand the key interventions introduced by the policy. 5 4 3 2 1
4. The policy is relevant to addressing the migration of doctors in Nigeria. 5 4 3 2
1
5. The implementation of the policy is noticeable in my hospital. 5 4 3 2 1
6. I have participated in or benefited from programmes related to the NPHWM. 5 4 3
2 1
7. The hospital management has provided updates or training sessions on the policy. 5 4
3 2 1
8. The NPHWM has influenced my view about remaining in Nigeria. 5 4 3 2 1

SECTION C: ASSESSMENT OF NPHWM INTERVENTIONS

A. Incentives and Welfare

1. The policy has improved my salary or allowance structure. 5 4 3 2 1
2. Access to credit or mortgage facilities for doctors has improved. 5 4 3 2 1
3. The working environment and availability of equipment have improved. 5 4 3 2
1
4. Work-related insurance or health coverage has been strengthened. 5 4 3 2 1
5. Visible welfare schemes for doctors now exist in public hospitals. 5 4 3 2 1

B. Capacity Building and Professional Development

1. There are more opportunities for professional training and development. 5 4 3 2
1
2. Residency and specialist training slots have increased since 2024. 5 4 3 2 1
3. Promotion and career progression are now more structured and transparent. 5 4 3
2 1
4. The policy has improved collaboration with international training bodies. 5 4 3 2
1
5. Mentorship and research capacity have been strengthened. 5 4 3 2 1

C. Digital Health and Technology Integration

1. There is improved access to digital tools for clinical practice. 5 4 3 2 1
2. Telemedicine and electronic record systems have become more available. 5 4 3 2
1
3. I have received training on using digital health tools. 5 4 3 2 1
4. Digital health has reduced workload or enhanced efficiency. 5 4 3 2 1
5. The policy's digital health interventions have improved my job satisfaction. 5 4 3
2 1

D. Work-Life Balance, Wellbeing, and Safety

1. My hospital has improved staff safety and security measures. 5 4 3 2 1
2. There is reduced exposure to workplace violence or harassment. 5 4 3 2 1

3. Workload distribution has become fairer and more manageable. 5 4 3 2 1
4. My hospital promotes mental health and stress management for doctors. 5 4 3 2
1
5. My work-life balance has improved since the introduction of the NPHWM. 5 4 3
2 1

E. Return, Readmission, and Diaspora Engagement

1. The NPHWM has made it easier for Nigerian doctors abroad to return to practice. 5 4
3 2 1
2. Returning doctors are better integrated into the public system. 5 4 3 2 1
3. Diaspora collaboration programmes (training, mentorship) are active in my hospital. 5
4 3 2 1
4. I believe diaspora involvement can strengthen the Nigerian health system. 5 4 3 2
1
5. I am aware of colleagues who have returned through government support programmes. 5
4 3 2 1

F. International Collaboration and Ethical Recruitment

1. The NPHWM has strengthened bilateral agreements with destination countries. 5 4
3 2 1
2. The policy has improved the monitoring of international recruitment practices. 5 4 3
2 1

3. Foreign recruitment agencies now comply better with ethical recruitment standards. 5
4 3 2 1
4. International collaboration with foreign governments and agencies has increased. 5 4
3 2 1
5. Destination countries now contribute more to Nigeria's health workforce development. 5
4 3 2 1

G. Rural and Underserved Area Support

1. Incentives for rural postings (allowances, bonuses) have improved. 5 4 3 2 1
2. Infrastructure in rural or underserved hospitals has improved. 5 4 3 2 1
3. Accommodation and amenities for rural postings are better than before. 5 4 3 2
1
4. The career credit system for rural service is being implemented. 5 4 3 2 1
5. Staffing shortages in rural or underserved hospitals have reduced. 5 4 3 2 1

SECTION D: DOCTOR RETENTION AND INTENTION TO MIGRATE

1. I am satisfied with my current job in this hospital. 5 4 3 2 1
2. I intend to remain in public service for the next three years. 5 4 3 2 1
3. I have considered migrating abroad within the past year. 5 4 3 2 1
4. Improved policy implementation would increase my likelihood of staying. 5 4 3 2
1
5. My hospital management plays an active role in retaining doctors. 5 4 3 2 1

6. The NPHWM has had a positive influence on my decision to stay. 5 4 3 2 1

7. Overall, the policy has improved retention rates among doctors in Edo State. 5 4 3
2 1

SECTION E: SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Please provide any suggestions or recommendations on how the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration can be improved to enhance doctor retention in Nigeria:

Appendix III
Reliability Test Results

Case Processing Summary

	N	%
Valid	17	100.0
Cases Excluded ^a	0	.0
Total	17	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardised Items	N of Items
.955	.956	50

Appendix IV

ETHICAL APPROVAL

EDO STATE MINISTRY OF HEALTH
HEALTH RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

PROTOCOL NUMBER HA/737/25/C/11281023 (PLEASE QUOTE IN ALL ENQUIRIES)

APPROVAL NUMBER HA/737/25/C/12011023

TITLE OF RESEARCH PROPOSAL ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF THE NATIONAL POLICY ON HEALTH WORKFORCE MIGRATION ON DOCTOR RETENTION RATES IN PUBLIC HOSPITALS IN EDO STATE

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (S) OSADOLOR AISOSA JUNIOR

DATE CONSIDERED 1ST DECEMBER, 2025.

DECISION OF THE COMMITTEE APPROVED

THIS APPROVAL DATES 01/12/2025 TO 01/12/2026. IF THERE IS A DELAY IN STARTING THE RESEARCH, PLEASE INFORM THE HREC EDO SMOH SO THAT THE DATES OF APPROVAL CAN BE ADJUSTED ACCORDINGLY

REMARK: Please kindly note that the HREC Edo SMOH seal authenticates this approval

DR (MRS) Omonyemen B. BELLO
(MBBS, MPH, FPHCM) (CHAIRMAN)

Bello
31/12/2025
SIGNATURE & DATE.....

SUPERVISOR(S)

ATTESTATION BY INVESTIGATOR(S)

No participant accrual or activity related to this research may be conducted outside of the approval dates. All informed consent forms used in this study must carry the Edo SMOH HREC-assigned number and duration of your research. No changes are permitted in the research without prior approval of the Edo SMOH HREC except in circumstances outlined in the Code. The Edo SMOH HREC reserves the right to conduct compliance visits to your research site without previous notification.

[Signature] 10/12/2025
Signature & Date.....

✉ edohrec@edostate.gov.ng

📍 Room 16, Block D, 2nd floor, State secretariat building.

